

1D two-phase, non-isothermal modeling of a zero-gap alkaline carbon dioxide electrolyzer: Effect of operating conditions and cathode flooding

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ABSTRACT

A one-dimensional, two-phase, non-isothermal multiphysics model of a zero-gap alkaline CO₂ electrolyzer is developed and validated to capture coupled transport, carbonate chemistry, and reaction kinetics. High ethylene selectivity is confined to a narrow operating window controlled by water management, CO₂ availability, and ionic transport. Cathode hydration is identified as a key governing factor. Insufficient hydration limits ionic conductivity and promotes hydrogen evolution, whereas over-hydration induces flooding, restricts gas transport, and accelerates carbonation. Increasing temperature enhances kinetics but shifts selectivity toward hydrogen, while increasing pressure improves CO₂ supply but favors formate formation via hydroxide depletion. These results establish that optimal performance requires a precise balance between hydration, gas transport, and carbonate chemistry, providing quantitative guidance for operation and control.

1. Introduction

The electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂RR) is increasingly recognized as a cornerstone technology within carbon capture and utilization, enabling the conversion of CO₂ into fuels and chemical feedstocks (e.g., CO, formate, ethylene, alcohols) using renewable electricity under mild conditions with modular scalability [1–3]. Compared to thermocatalytic or photochemical routes, CO₂RR offers precise control via applied potential, is inherently compatible with intermittent renewables, and benefits from continuous advances in electrolyzer architectures—progressing from H-cells and flow cells to zero-gap membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs) that minimize ohmic losses and mass-transfer resistance [4–6]. Despite this promise, moving from laboratory demonstrations to industrial relevance demands simultaneous gains in current density, cell voltage, Faradaic efficiency (FE), and durability, particularly for multi-carbon (C₂⁺) products that require efficient C–C coupling and careful suppression of the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [7,8].

Among the available cathode materials, copper (Cu) is unique in its ability to synthesize C₂⁺ products, especially ethylene (C₂H₄), at practically meaningful partial current densities, a feature attributed to its intermediate *CO binding and propensity for C–C coupling [9–11]. This has led to a focus on Cu catalyst design (facets, nanostructures, oxide-derived phases) and reactor engineering to meet technological targets for CO₂-to-C₂ processes [12–14]. In tandem, zero-gap

MEAs have accelerated performance by shortening ionic paths and engineering gas–liquid–solid interfaces within gas-diffusion electrodes (GDEs), reaching industrially relevant current densities with improved selectivity compared with single-gap flow cells [6,15].

Selectivity on Cu is governed as much by cell and electrode design as by catalyst composition. Systematic comparisons show that the membrane, flow-field geometry, and humidification strategy reshape the local microenvironment (pH, *CO coverage, water activity) and can swing ethylene selectivity from near zero to ~ 70% on the same Cu motif, evidence that architecture and transport often exert a stronger influence than nominal “active sites” [3,5,6]. Consistent with this, spatially resolved studies on large-area Cu GDEs reveal selectivity gradients along the channel: HER increases downstream as CO partial pressure falls, while ethylene selectivity remains comparatively stable—key insights for scale-up and reactor uniformity [16,17]. Moreover, zero-gap experiments with Cu nanocubes confirm that high ethylene FE can be sustained at elevated current densities, but they also underscore the sensitivity to flooding and double-layer dynamics at practical rates [18–20].

Electrolyte and electric-double-layer (EDL) effects are equally decisive. In alkaline/neutral AEM-MEAs, larger alkali cations (K⁺, Cs⁺) generally promote CO₂RR kinetics and C₂⁺ formation by shaping interfacial solvation and sustaining high local pH, whereas acidic environments suppress carbonate formation but intensify HER unless the

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microenvironment is engineered via cation management or buffering layers [21–23]. Recent operando spectroscopy in acidic media demonstrates that cations modulate *CO_2 adsorption and interfacial water reorganization on Cu, clarifying why selective CO_2RR is possible even at low bulk pH when local conditions (current density, cation identity) are tuned appropriately; organic interlayers can further shift the local pH/selectivity balance [24].

Operating temperature and pressure are powerful levers for Cu-MEA performance. In zero-gap devices with Cu GDEs, raising the temperature improves ionic conductivity and mass transport but can shift selectivity from C_2^+ toward CO/H_2 beyond ~ 50 °C, coincident with reduced surface *CO coverage and possible Cu surface reconstruction; thus, there exists a catalyst- and product-specific temperature window for maximizing C_2^+ formation [25,26]. More broadly, MEA studies (Cu and Ag exemplars) show that device efficiency often improves with temperature, while water balance and stability depend sensitively on heating protocols—important as commercial stacks will operate hotter due to ohmic heating [27]. Pressure and flow-field-controlled residence times further affect *CO pooling and, consequently, C–C coupling on Cu. By tailoring flow-field architecture and flow rate, C_2^+ selectivity $> 80\%$ at 0.2 A cm^{-2} can be achieved, with parts of the catalyst operating effectively as a CO-to- C_2 reactor within a CO_2 electrolyzer [16,28,29].

Achieving durable Cu-MEA operation requires addressing salt precipitation and cathode flooding, failure modes tightly coupled to carbonate chemistry and water transport [30]. In situ X-ray studies directly link $KHCO_3$ precipitation inside the GDE to pore blockage, oscillatory wetting, and temporary HER surges, clarifying how salts and water dynamics co-evolve during instability episodes [15]. Perspectives and systematic studies now map mitigation strategies to ion solubility and transport: controlling cation species and accumulation, anolyte concentration, membrane thickness, and especially temperature with proper humidification (e.g., $T > 50$ °C) can suppress salt formation for > 144 h at 0.2 A cm^{-2} , pointing to operational pathways toward stable, high-rate Cu electrolysis [31–33]. In parallel, Cu instability, including dissolution/redeposition and oxidation-state cycling, contributes to C_2 loss. Operando microscopies reveal Cu relocation within GDEs and show that, under strongly alkaline conditions, flooding often dominates the observed decline in C_2^+ selectivity over time, motivating materials and operating strategies to harden Cu against reconstruction [34,35].

While AEM-MEAs have set many of the present benchmarks for Cu-cathode rates and C_2^+ selectivity, they incur inherent CO_2 “scavenging” to (bi)carbonate, lowering carbon efficiency and complicating separations. Bipolar-membrane (BPM) MEAs promise higher carbon utilization and precious-metal-free anodes but presently face penalties in FE and voltage that are the subject of active research (thinner BPMs, improved water-dissociation catalysts, and microenvironment engineering) [22]. Device-level innovations, such as more hydrophobic gas diffusion layers (GDLs), are being pursued to enhance durability and energy efficiency for Cu-to- C_2 operation in zero-gap cells [36, 37]. Meanwhile, Cu-in-MEA reviews distill progress in morphology control, oxide-derived copper, alloying/heterostructures, and ionomer interactions, and call for tighter integration of operational stressors (T , p , RH) with surface evolution and degradation models to guide commercialization [38].

Collectively, these findings motivate an integrated experiments-plus-modeling approach to quantify how operating conditions (temperature, pressure, inlet humidity, electrolyte composition/pH, and flow-field-defined residence times) govern Cu-cathode flooding, carbonate formation, ionic/ohmic losses, and C_2^+ selectivity in zero-gap MEAs [39,40]. Multiphysics models that couple electrochemistry, two-phase transport, heat effects, and acid–base/carbonate equilibria can delineate regimes that maximize CO_2 utilization and energy efficiency while minimizing Cu-specific degradation phenomena [41]. Relevant works on CO_2RR modeling presented in the literature are reviewed below.

Modeling and optimization of GDE and MEA CO_2RR systems have undergone rapid advancements in recent years. Foundational work by Weng et al. [42] (2018) introduced a multiphysics 1D GDE model that resolves gas transport, electrolyte wetting, and CO_2 –carbonate chemistry, demonstrating how local saturation, porosity, and hydrophobicity govern mass-transfer limitations and catalyst utilization. This framework was extended to MEA architectures in Weng et al. [43] (2019), establishing the dominant role of carbonate transport, membrane hydration, and ion migration in determining CO_2 utilization and voltage efficiency, and revealing dehydration-driven performance decay in vapor-fed MEAs. Their subsequent work on Cu-MEA systems (Weng et al. [41], 2020) incorporated multiproduct kinetics and water-activity-dependent selectivity, showing strong spatial non-uniformities and highlighting the interplay between catalyst layer (CL) thickness, ionomer content, and operating temperature. To address 1D limitations, Yang et al. [44] (2021) introduced a 2D multiphase GDE model validated against experiments, capturing along-the-channel CO_2 depletion, flow-field effects, and geometrical upscaling behavior. This model quantified design trade-offs in porosity, catalyst loading, and gas-feed composition, demonstrating the scalability of formate-producing GDEs under optimized flow and pressure profiles. Recent studies extend modeling into degradation, stability, and advanced MEA microenvironments. Ehlinger et al. [45] (2024) reported early-stage GDE activity loss due to catalyst agglomeration and hydrophobicity decay, identifying architectural vulnerabilities that models must capture. Ertugrul et al. [46] (2025) used a 1D Cu-MEA model to quantify how CL thickness and electrochemically active surface area modulate local potential gradients and C_2H_4 selectivity, enabling techno-economic analysis of ethylene-selective MEAs. Wang et al. [47] (2025) revealed salt-precipitation-driven instability in MEAs, showing how (bi)carbonate migrates and solidifies within GDE pores, ultimately obstructing CO_2 transport.

Together, these studies establish a clear evolution in the modeling of CO_2 electrolyzers, progressing from early one-dimensional mechanistic descriptions toward increasingly spatially resolved, stability-aware, and microscopically informed frameworks that couple transport, electrochemistry, wetting, degradation, and device-scale effects. As summarized in Table 1, most current COMSOL-based studies emphasize 2D or 3D spatial resolution to investigate specific phenomena such as geometry-induced electric-field effects, gas-phase mass transport in GDEs, substrate-dependent diffusion pathways, thermal effects at the MEA level, or local electric–thermal field enhancement at catalyst interfaces. While these approaches provide important insight into localized or geometry-driven effects, they generally focus on a limited subset of the governing physics and therefore address individual phenomena in relative isolation. In contrast, the present work adopts a 1D formulation to enable the full and consistent coupling of multiphase transport, detailed carbonate chemistry, non-isothermal operation, flooding dynamics, and multiproduct reaction kinetics under realistic zero-gap conditions. Rather than prioritizing spatial resolution, the proposed framework emphasizes physicochemical completeness, allowing the identification of the dominant cross-couplings governing system-level performance, voltage breakdown, hydration balance, and Cu-based CO_2 selectivity. In this sense, the model complements existing spatially resolved COMSOL studies by providing a physically consistent foundation capable of capturing the coupled mechanisms that define the operational window of zero-gap alkaline CO_2 electrolyzers. This framework provides a robust basis for future extensions toward 2D and 3D implementations incorporating local geometric and flow-field effects.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the 1D, two-phase, non-isothermal model formulation, detailing the governing transport equations, electrochemical kinetics, thermodynamic relations, and boundary conditions used to resolve heat, mass, and charge transport within the zero-gap MEA architecture. Section 3 describes the case studies and parametric variations considered,

Table 1
2D/3D modeling works presented in the literature.

Reference	System	Dimension	Modeling platform	Target products	Main physics	Contribution
[48]	PV-EC	2D	COMSOL Multiphysics	CO/general	optical-electrical-electrochemical	photo-electrochemical coupling
[49]	cell	3D	COMSOL Multiphysics	CO ₂ RR products (general)	geometry-electric field	geometry-induced electric-field effects
[50]	GDE	2D	COMSOL Multiphysics	CO, C ₂ products	mass-charge-momentum	GDE transport analysis
[51]	MEA	3D	FEM model	CO ₂ RR products (general)	electrochemical-thermal	thermal effects in MEA
[52]	GDE/substrate	2D	COMSOL Multiphysics	CO, C ₂ ⁺ products	gas-solid transport	effect of substrate on CO ₂ /CO transport
[53]	catalyst	2D (local)	COMSOL Multiphysics	C ₂ ⁺ products (C ₂ H ₄ , EtOH)	electric-thermal (local)	local electric-thermal field enhancement

including operating temperature, inlet humidity, electrolyte pH, pressure, and flow-field conditions relevant to Cu-based CO₂RR. Section 4 provides an in-depth discussion of the results, examining the interplay between operating conditions, local microenvironment, cathode flooding, carbonate formation, and the resulting impacts on Cu-catalyzed C₂⁺ selectivity and voltage breakdown. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2. Model formulation

As shown in Fig. 1, the numerical domain accounts for a comprehensive 1D description of transport and reactive processes across the MEA (x -coordinate) of an alkaline CO₂ electrolyzer fed with a KOH solution at the anode and humidified CO₂ at the cathode. The mathematical formulation includes, but is not limited to: (i) CO₂ carbonation reactions, (ii) multiproduct CO₂ reduction, (iii) OH⁻ consumption and generation, (iv) multicomponent transport, (v) liquid water transport, and (vi) gas oxygen transport. The MEA is composed of six layers: (i) anode PTL, aptl; (ii) anode catalyst layer, acl; (iii) anion-exchange membrane, aem; (iv) cathode catalyst layer, ccl; (v) cathode microporous layer, cmpl; and (vi) cathode gas diffusion layer, cgdl. Note that the AEM is employed to sustain alkaline operation by transporting OH⁻ ions, which promotes C₂ product formation and suppresses hydrogen evolution; additionally, it enables (bi)carbonate transport arising from CO₂ carbonation, physically separates anodic and cathodic products, and reduces ohmic losses in the zero-gap configuration. The anode PTL is included to ensure uniform electrolyte distribution, enable effective oxygen removal, and provide electronic conduction and mechanical support, thereby capturing relevant two-phase transport effects under practical operating conditions. External boundary conditions are established at the PTL and GDL interfaces with the bipolar plates (BPPs).

2.1. Assumptions

The main simplifying assumptions of the model are:

- Steady state operation and ideal gases.
- AEM is perfectly impermeable to liquid and gas species other than dissolved CO₂ and formate.
- Effective drag transport in the electrolyte is characterized by a term proportional to the current density. It is described based on an effective water-transport parameter rather than on the complex multicomponent flux of ionic species.
- Species transport is well described by dilute solution theory.
- Components of the MEA are macroscopically homogeneous.
- Interfacial electrical, thermal and mass transport resistances are negligible.

- Convective heat transport in the MEA is negligible compared to heat conduction.
- Electrochemical kinetics obey Tafel kinetics.
- Representative average water saturations are prescribed at the aptl/abpp and cgdl/cbpp interfaces according to capillary pressure curves.

Other considerations are common to previous modeling works and can be found elsewhere [41–43,46].

2.2. Conservation equations

The formulation is composed of nineteen conservation equations (corresponding to nineteen solution variables), namely: (i) electrons (electronic potential, ϕ_e) (ii) electrolyte-phase charge, (ionic potential, ϕ_ℓ); (iii) electrolyte water content (dissolved water, λ); (iv) energy (temperature, T); (v) liquid-phase mass (liquid pressure, p_l); (vi) gas-phase mass (gas pressure, p_g); (vii)–(xi) charged species (hydroxide concentration, C_{OH^-} , proton concentration, C_{H^+} , formate concentration, C_{HCOO^-} , bicarbonate concentration, $C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$, carbonate concentration, $C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$); (xii)–(xv) uncharged liquid-phase species (dissolved CO₂ concentration, $C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$, formic acid concentration, C_{HCOOH} , ethanol concentration, $C_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$, propanol concentration, $C_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$); and (xvi)–(xix) uncharged gas-phase species (water vapor molar fraction, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, CO₂ molar fraction, x_{CO_2} , CO molar fraction, x_{CO} , ethylene molar fraction, $x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$). The expressions for each type of equation are presented below, while the values of the transport properties and reactive parameters that were assumed to be constant are provided in the Supplementary Information [41–43,45,46].

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\sigma_e^{\text{eff}} \frac{d\phi_e}{dx} \right) = S_e \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\sigma_\ell^{\text{eff}} \frac{d\phi_\ell}{dx} \right) = S_\ell \quad (1b)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\frac{D_\lambda^{\text{eff}}}{V_m} \frac{d\lambda}{dx} + \frac{n_d^w}{F} j_\ell + \frac{\lambda}{V_m} \frac{K_{m,l}}{\mu_l} \frac{(p_{l,a} - p_{l,c})}{\delta_{\text{aem}}} \right) = S_\lambda; \quad j_\ell = -\sigma_\ell^{\text{eff}} \frac{d\phi_\ell}{dx} \quad (1c)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-k^{\text{eff}} \frac{dT}{dx} \right) = S_T \quad (1d)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\frac{\rho_l K k_{r1}}{\mu_l} \frac{dp_l}{dx} \right) = S_l \quad (1e)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\frac{\rho_g K k_{rg}}{\mu_g} \frac{dp_g}{dx} \right) = S_g \quad (1f)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}} \frac{dC_i}{dx} + u_i C_i - \frac{z_i F D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}}}{RT} C_i \frac{d\phi_\ell}{dx} \right) = S_{i,l}^c; \quad u_i = -\frac{K K_{r1}}{\mu_l} \frac{dp_l}{dx} \quad (1g)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic of the numerical domain, indicating the x -coordinate of the 1D model, the layers of the MEA, and the main transport and reactive processes included in the formulation.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}} \frac{dC_i}{dx} + u_l C_i \right) = S_{i,l}; \quad u_l = -\frac{K K_{rl}}{\mu_l} \frac{dp_l}{dx} \quad (1h)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-D_{i,g}^{\text{eff}} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{x_i}{M_g} \right) + u_g x_i C_g \right) = S_{i,g}; \quad u_g = -\frac{K K_{rg}}{\mu_g} \frac{dp_g}{dx} \quad (1i)$$

where σ_e^{eff} is the effective electrical conductivity, σ_e^{eff} is the effective ionic conductivity, $D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}}$ is the effective diffusivity of dissolved water in the electrolyte, n_d^w is the electro-osmotic drag (EOD) coefficient of dissolved water, $K_{m,l}$ is the hydraulic permeability of water in the electrolyte, $V_m = (IEC \rho_m)^{-1}$ is the molar volume of the electrolyte, with IEC as the ionic-exchange capacity and ρ_m as the density, j_e is the ionic current density, μ_l and ρ_l are the viscosity and density of liquid water, μ_g is the viscosity of the gas phase, δ_{aem} is the AEM thickness, $p_{l,a}$ and $p_{l,c}$ are the liquid-phase pressures of the anode and the cathode compartments, k^{eff} is the effective thermal conductivity, K is the permeability, k_{rl} and k_{rg} are the liquid- and gas-phase relative permeabilities, $D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}}$ and $D_{i,g}^{\text{eff}}$ are the effective diffusivities of liquid/gas species i , u_l and u_g are the liquid- and gas-phase superficial velocities, z_i is the charge number of species i , M_g and C_g are the molecular mass and total concentration of the gas phase, F is Faraday's constant, R is the universal gas constant, and S_k is the source term of equation k .

The density, ρ_g , total molar concentration, C_g , and mass fraction of species i , Y_i , of the gas phase (O_2 , H_2O and CO_2 at the anode, and H_2 , H_2O , CO , CO_2 and C_2H_4 at the cathode) are given by the ideal gas law

$$\rho_g = \frac{p_g M_g}{RT}; \quad C_g = \frac{p_g}{RT}; \quad Y_i = \frac{x_i M_i}{M_g} \quad (2a)$$

where the molecular mass is

$$M_g = \sum_{i=1}^N x_i M_i \quad (2b)$$

Oxygen and hydrogen are considered the most abundant gas species at the anode and the cathode, respectively. Their mole fractions are

simply determined as $x_{O_2} = 1 - x_{H_2O} - x_{CO_2}$ and $x_{H_2} = 1 - x_{H_2O} - x_{CO} - x_{CO_2} - x_{C_2H_4}$.

2.3. Constitutive relationships

The constitutive relationships used in the model are presented below, including the formulation adopted for the description of mass diffusivity, the effect of water saturation and capillary pressure, and the transport properties in the electrolyte.

2.3.1. Mass diffusivity

The dry effective diffusivity of gas species (H_2O , CO , CO_2 , C_2H_4) in the porous layers of the MEA, considering the Bosanquet formula, is given by [54–56]

$$D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,dry}} = \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau} \left(\frac{1}{D_{i,g}^{\text{bulk}}} + \frac{1}{D_{i,g}^{\text{kn}}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3a)$$

where ε and τ are the porosity and tortuosity factor of the layer under consideration, and $D_{i,g}^{\text{bulk}}$ and $D_{i,g}^{\text{kn}}$ are the bulk and Knudsen diffusivities of species i , respectively.

According to the Stefan–Maxwell theory, the bulk diffusivity of species i in the multicomponent gas mixture is equal to [41,43]

$$D_{i,g}^{\text{bulk}} = \frac{1 - Y_i}{\sum_{n \neq i}^N \frac{Y_n}{D_{i,n}}} \quad (3b)$$

where the binary gas-phase diffusivity is estimated as a function of pressure and temperature from the Fuller–Schettler–Giddings correlation [57]

$$D_{i,n} [\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}] = \frac{10^{-3} T [\text{K}]^{1.75} (M_i [\text{g mol}^{-1}] + M_n [\text{g mol}^{-1}])^{0.5}}{p [\text{atm}] \left(\nu_{p,i}^{0.33} + \nu_{p,n}^{0.33} \right)^2} \quad (3c)$$

The Knudsen diffusivity accounts for the frequent collision of gas molecules i with walls in narrow pores [54,55]

$$D_{i,g}^{\text{kn}} = \left(\frac{2r_p}{3} \right) \sqrt{\frac{8RT}{\pi M_i}} \quad (3d)$$

where r_p is the pore radius.

The wet effective diffusivity of neutral (HCOOH , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$, CO_2^{aq}) and ionic (HCOO^- , OH^- , H^+ , HCO_3^- , CO_3^{2-}) liquid species is affected by the porosity and tortuosity factor of the considered porous layer and temperature as [58]

$$D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,wet}} = \frac{\varepsilon}{\tau} D_{i,l}^{\text{ref}} \exp \left[\frac{E_{i,w}^{\text{d}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where $D_{i,l}^{\text{ref}}$ and E_i are the reference diffusivity and activation energy, respectively (see the Supplementary Information).

2.3.2. Effect of water saturation on transport properties and capillary pressure

The effective diffusivity of gas species i under two-phase conditions is corrected by the relative effective diffusivity. According to García-Salaberri et al. [56], a cubic power law is considered

$$D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,tp}} = \frac{D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,tp}}}{D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,dry}}} D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,dry}} = (1-s)^3 D_{i,g}^{\text{eff,dry}} \quad (5)$$

where s is the liquid saturation.

Similarly, the effective diffusivity of liquid species i under two-phase conditions is corrected as [59,60]

$$D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,tp}} = \frac{D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,tp}}}{D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,wet}}} D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,wet}} = s^3 D_{i,l}^{\text{eff,wet}} \quad (6)$$

The liquid- and gas-phase relative permeabilities, $k_{r,l}$, and $k_{r,g}$, are modeled by cubic power laws of the form [61]

$$k_{r,l} = s_{\text{red}}^3; \quad k_{r,g} = (1-s_{\text{red}})^3 \quad (7)$$

where s_{red} is the reduced liquid saturation, $s_{\text{red}} = (s-s_r)/(1-s_r)$, with s_r being the residual or immobile saturation. That is, s_r accounts for liquid water that does not participate in capillary transport and phase change during operation, for example, due to the existence of disconnected clusters [62].

The increase of the effective thermal conductivity of the PTL and GDL with liquid saturation is modeled based on the work of Xu et al. [63] with commercial carbon-fiber papers. The impact of liquid saturation on the thermal conductivity of thin CLs and MPL was neglected. The thermal conductivity varies almost linearly according to the expression

$$k_{\text{aprl}}^{\text{eff,tp}} [\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}] = k_{\text{aprl}}^{\text{eff,dry}} + 1.4s \quad (8a)$$

$$k_{\text{cgdl}}^{\text{eff,tp}} [\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}] = k_{\text{cgdl}}^{\text{eff,dry}} + 1.4s \quad (8b)$$

where $k_{\text{aprl}}^{\text{eff,dry}} = 0.5 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{cgdl}}^{\text{eff,dry}} = 0.3 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ are the effective thermal conductivities under dry conditions.

The gas phase, mainly composed of oxygen generated from the OER, is the secondary phase at the anode, whereas liquid water is the secondary phase at the cathode. Hence, capillary pressure, defined as $p_c = p_l - p_g$, must be negative in the anode due to the higher pressure of gas bubbles compared to the surrounding liquid phase ($p_g > p_l$). In contrast, the capillary pressure in the cathode must be positive ($p_l > p_g$) [59,64]. This scenario is modeled using the $p_c - s$ curves presented by Gostick et al. [62] for the water-air fluid pair in carbon-fiber papers. The curve corresponding to water withdrawal is used at the anode and the curve corresponding to water injection is used at the cathode. Liquid saturation in both cases is expressed as

$$s = \sum_{i=1}^2 f_i [s_i (s_m - s_r) + s_r] \quad (9)$$

where s_i is the saturation given by the van Genuchten's (vG's) equations

$$s_i = \left[1 + \left(\frac{-p_c + p_{\text{ref}}}{p_{\text{cb},i}} \right)^{m_i} \right]^{-n_i} \quad (\text{water withdrawal, anode}) \quad (10a)$$

$$s_i = 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{p_c + p_{\text{ref}}}{p_{\text{cb},i}} \right)^{m_i} \right]^{-n_i} \quad (\text{water injection, cathode}) \quad (10b)$$

In these expressions, f_i is the proportionality factor of the i th curve to the total curve, s_r is the residual saturation at highly negative capillary pressure, s_m is the maximum water saturation achieved at large positive capillary pressure, and $p_{\text{cb},i}$, m_i and n_i are fitting parameters to experimental data.

2.3.3. Transport properties in the electrolyte

The effective diffusivity of ionic species (OH^- , H^+ , HCOO^- , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-}) in electrolyte-containing layers (i.e., AEM and CLs) was reduced compared to that corresponding to liquid water due to hindered transport through the electrolyte phase. The expression for the effective diffusivity of OH^- in the AEM and CLs as a function of temperature is given by [41–43,46,58]

$$D_{\text{OH}^-,m}^{\text{eff}} = D_{\text{OH}^-,m}^{\text{ref}} \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{OH}^-,m}^{\text{d}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

where $D_{\text{OH}^-,m}^{\text{ref}} = 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ is the reference diffusivity of OH^- in the electrolyte at room temperature ($T \approx 25^\circ \text{C}$), a factor of 5 lower than that in water ($D_{\text{OH}^-,w}^{\text{ref}} = 5.27 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

The diffusivity of the remaining ionic species was determined based on that of OH^- by applying a reduction factor $f_{i,m}$, so that

$$D_{i,m}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{D_{\text{OH}^-,m}^{\text{eff}}}{f_{i,m}} \quad (12)$$

A higher reduction factor was considered for H^+ due to the exclusion caused by the positive charge of the functional groups of the electrolyte ($f_{\text{H}^+,m} = 10$). For negative species (HCOO^- , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-}), the reduction factor was fixed at $f_{i,-m} = 4$.

Using a similar approach, the effective diffusivity of dissolved CO_2 in the AEM and CL was reduced with respect to that in free water

$$D_{\text{CO}_2,m}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{D_{\text{CO}_2,m}^{\text{ref}}}{f_{\text{CO}_2,m}} \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{CO}_2,m}^{\text{d}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (13)$$

where the reduction factor is $f_{\text{CO}_2,m} = 5$.

According to previous works [41,43,59], the correlations used for the effective ionic conductivity, effective diffusivity of water, EOD coefficient of water, and equilibrium water content are as follows

$$\sigma_\ell^{\text{eff}} = \varepsilon_m^3 4.04 (f_v - 0.06)^{1.5} \left(\frac{\text{pH}}{10} \right)^{1.2} \exp \left[\frac{E_\sigma}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (14a)$$

$$f_v = \frac{\lambda V_w}{\lambda V_w + V_m} \quad (14b)$$

$$n_d^w = f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}} \frac{\lambda}{15} \quad (14c)$$

$$D_\lambda^{\text{eff}} = \varepsilon_m^{1.5} \frac{1.123\lambda^3 - 9.365\lambda^2 + 19.807\lambda}{\lambda^3 - 2.115\lambda^2 - 33.013\lambda + 103.37} \times 10^{-10} \exp \left[\frac{E_\lambda}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (14d)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{eq}} = (0.05 + 20.45\text{RH} - 42.8\text{RH}^2 + 36\text{RH}^3) \left[1 + 0.2\text{RH}^2 \left(\frac{T - 303.1}{30} \right) \right] \quad (14e)$$

where ε_m is the electrolyte volume fraction ($\varepsilon_m = 1$ in the AEM and $\varepsilon_m < 1$ in the CLs), f_v is the volume fraction of water in the electrolyte, $f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}}$ is the effective multiplicative factor of the EOD coefficient, $\text{RH} = x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} p_g / p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}$ is the relative humidity, and E_σ and E_λ are the activation energies for ionic conduction and water diffusion in the electrolyte, respectively. Note that the ionic conductivity increases with the electrolyte alkalinity, even though it is significantly lower than that of proton-exchange electrolytes due to the lower mobility of ionic species and carbonation in AEMs under CO_2 RR conditions [65,66].

An aspect that deserves further attention is the electro-osmotic drag formulation adopted in the model, represented through the effective coefficient $n_d^w = f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}} (\lambda/15)$, which appears in the dissolved-water

balance as a current-driven flux term (Eq. (1c)). This formulation treats $f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}}$ as a signed, tunable parameter that captures the net water transport resulting from several concurrent mechanisms observed in zero-gap CO_2 electrolyzers. Although previous modeling studies generally report that the intrinsic EOD associated with anion migration points toward the anode [41,43], recent investigations also show that the overall water flux often reverses toward the cathode at practical current densities due to additional effects, most notably the inverse EOD associated with alkali-cation crossover, the strong water retention caused by (bi)carbonate formation and salt precipitation in the cathode GDE, and current-induced water uptake of the membrane/ionomer [35, 65,67,68]. Because these processes can outweigh the membrane-level EOD and are highly dependent on load, electrolyte composition, and CO_2 availability, using a single adjustable factor allows the model to span regimes ranging from cathode dehydration ($f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}} < 0$) to cathode flooding ($f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}} > 0$), without modifying the underlying transport physics. Thus, $f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}}$ should be interpreted as an effective through-plane water-transport parameter, enabling controlled exploration of experimentally observed transitions from anode-biased to cathode-biased net water flow, and allowing the identification of the hydration window in which CO_2 accessibility, ionic conductivity, and carbonate chemistry remain optimally balanced.

The saturation pressure of water depends exponentially on temperature [59]

$$\log(p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}) = 23.1963 - \frac{3816.44}{T - 46.13} \quad (15)$$

2.4. Source terms

The source terms S_k of the system of conservation Eqs. (1a)–(1i) are listed in the Supplementary Information. The charge-transfer terms introduced by electrochemical reactions, homogeneous reactions due to carbonation and formate protonation, phase change and sorption/desorption of water, CO_2 dissolution, and heat generation are presented below.

2.4.1. Charge-transfer reactions

The electrochemical reactions include the alkaline and acidic OER at the anode, as well as the HER and CO_2 reduction to five main products at the cathode: carbon monoxide, CO, formate, HCOO^- , ethylene, C_2H_4 , ethanol, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, and propanol $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$. Tafel kinetics are considered for all species, which provides a good approximation at high overpotentials [41,45].

Anode

Cathode

At the anode, first-order kinetics are assumed for the volumetric reaction rate of the alkaline and acidic OER, with a linear dependency on liquid saturation. Consequently, the electrochemical reaction is hindered when gas blockage by oxygen bubbles and other gaseous species increases excessively [41,43,59,69].

$$j_{\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}} = a_a s i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}} \left(\frac{C_{\text{OH}^-}}{C_{\text{OH}^-}^{\text{ref}}} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}} F}{RT} \eta_a \right) \quad (17a)$$

$$j_{\text{OER}}^{\text{ac}} = a_a s i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{ac}} \left(\frac{C_{\text{H}^+}}{C_{\text{H}^+}^{\text{ref}}} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{OER}}^{\text{ac}} F}{RT} \eta_a \right) \quad (17b)$$

In this expression, a_a is the specific surface area of the anode electrode, $C_{\text{OH}^-}^{\text{ref}}$ and $C_{\text{H}^+}^{\text{ref}}$ are the reference hydroxide and proton concentrations, and $i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}}/i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{ac}}$ and $\alpha_{\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}}/\alpha_{\text{OER}}^{\text{ac}}$ are the exchange current densities and transfer coefficients of the alkaline/acidic OER, respectively (see the Supplementary Information). The acidic OER becomes important when the OH^- concentration (pH) is significantly reduced at low KOH concentrations and/or high carbonation rates. The anode overpotential is defined as

$$\eta_a = \phi_e - \phi_\ell - U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}} \quad (17c)$$

where $U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}$ is the thermodynamic equilibrium voltage, which depends on temperature and pH according to the Nernst equation

$$U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}} = U_{0,\text{OER}} - 2.303 \frac{RT}{F} \text{pH} \quad (17d)$$

Here, $U_{0,\text{OER}}$ is the standard equilibrium potential for alkaline/acidic OER.

The alkaline/acidic OER exchange current density increases with temperature according to

$$i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{alk/ac}} = i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{ref,alk/ac}} \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{OER}}^{\text{k,alk/ac}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (17e)$$

where $i_{0,\text{OER}}^{\text{ref,alk/ac}}$ is the reference exchange current density at 25 °C, and $E_{\text{OER}}^{\text{k,alk/ac}}$ is the activation energy of the alkaline/acidic OER.

At the cathode, the volumetric current density of the HER is proportional to the effective water activity, $a_w^{\text{eff}} = \text{RH} + s$, which provides a quantification of the local water content (reactant). In addition, the exchange current density decreases nonlinearly with the pH ($n_{\text{ph}} > 1$), so that the selectivity toward H_2 decreases significantly in strong alkaline media [41,43,70].

$$i_{\text{HER}} = a_c (\text{RH} + s) \left(\frac{\text{pH}}{12} \right)^{-n_{\text{ph}}} i_{0,\text{HER}} \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{HER}} F}{RT} \eta_{\text{HER}} \right) \quad (18a)$$

where

$$i_{0,\text{HER}} = i_{0,\text{HER}}^{\text{ref}} \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{HER}}^{\text{k}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (18b)$$

On the contrary, the multiproduct volumetric reaction rate for CO_2 reduction to species k depends linearly on the availability of macroscopic gaseous transport routes through the term $(1-s)$, and is directly proportional to the dissolved CO_2 concentration, $C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}$. The reaction order is assumed to be equal to one for all species ($n_{\text{CO}_2} = 1$) except for formate, whose production has been shown to increase significantly at large cathode pressures ($n_{\text{CO}_2} > 1$) [29]. Besides, the kinetic expression includes a power-law relationship with RH to account for the beneficial effect of ionomer hydration rather than flooding on CO_2 reduction ($n_{\text{rh}} > 1$) [71].

$$i_k = a_c (1-s) \text{RH}^{n_{\text{rh}}} \left(\frac{C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}}{C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq,ref}}} \right)^{n_{\text{CO}_2}} i_{0,k} \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_k F}{RT} \eta_k \right) \quad (18c)$$

In the above expressions, a_c denotes the cathode specific surface area, and $i_{0,\text{HER}}/\alpha_{\text{HER}}$ and $i_{0,k}/\alpha_{0,k}$ are the exchange current densities/transfer coefficients of the HER and the k th CO_2 reduction reaction, respectively. The cathode overpotential is given by

$$\eta_{\text{HER}} = \phi_\ell - \phi_e - U_{\text{HER}}^{\text{eq}}; \quad \eta_k = \phi_\ell - \phi_e - U_k^{\text{eq}} \quad (18d)$$

where the thermodynamic equilibrium voltage is equal to

$$U_{\text{HER}}^{\text{eq}} = U_{0,\text{HER}} + 2.303 \frac{RT}{F} \text{pH}; \quad U_k^{\text{eq}} = U_{0,k} + 2.303 \frac{RT}{F} \text{pH}; \quad (18e)$$

The exchange current density of the k th CO_2 reduction reaction varies exponentially with temperature

$$i_{0,k} = i_{0,k}^{\text{ref}} \exp \left[\frac{E_k^{\text{k}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (18f)$$

where $i_{0,k}^{\text{ref}}$ and E_k^{E} are the reference exchange current density and activation energy for species k , respectively.

The total charge transfer rate due to electron consumption by the HER and CO₂ electro-reduction at the cathode is given by

$$S_{\text{ct}}^{\text{c}} = i_{\text{HER}} + i_{\text{CO}} + i_{\text{HCOO}^-} + i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4} + i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}} + i_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}, \quad (19\text{a})$$

while the total water consumption rate, hydroxide generation rate and CO₂ (aq) consumption rate at the cathode are

$$S_{\text{ct,w}}^{\text{c}} = -\frac{i_{\text{HER}}}{F} - \frac{i_{\text{CO}}}{2F} - \frac{i_{\text{HCOO}^-}}{2F} - \frac{2i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}}{3F} - \frac{3i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}}{4F} - \frac{13i_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}}{18F} \quad (19\text{b})$$

$$S_{\text{ct,OH}^-}^{\text{c}} = \frac{i_{\text{HER}}}{F} + \frac{i_{\text{CO}}}{F} + \frac{i_{\text{HCOO}^-}}{2F} + \frac{i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}}{F} + \frac{i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}}{F} + \frac{i_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}}{F} \quad (19\text{c})$$

$$S_{\text{ct,CO}_2}^{\text{c}} = -\frac{i_{\text{CO}}}{2F} - \frac{i_{\text{HCOO}^-}}{2F} - \frac{i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}}{6F} - \frac{i_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}}{6F} - \frac{3i_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}}{18F} \quad (19\text{d})$$

2.4.2. Homogeneous reactions

The homogeneous reactions in the liquid phase include fast acid–base equilibria that govern the speciation of aqueous CO₂ and its related carbonate species. Dissolved CO₂ undergoes hydration and proton-transfer reactions that interconvert CO₂ (aq), bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), and carbonate (CO₃²⁻), while also interacting with hydroxide ions generated during electrochemical reactions. In addition, water self-ionization and acid–base dissociation of formic acid contribute to the local proton and hydroxide balance. Together, these bulk reactions regulate the pH and the distribution of carbon species, strongly influencing both CO₂ availability and the competition between HER and CO₂RR [15,72].

The contribution of every homogeneous reaction n to the consumption or generation rate of species j , $S_{\text{h},j}$, can be expressed in condensed form as [41–43]

$$S_{\text{h},j} = \sum_n v_{j,n} \left(k_n \prod_{v_{j,n} < 0} C_j^{-v_{j,n}} - \frac{k_n}{K_n} \prod_{v_{j,n} > 0} C_j^{v_{j,n}} \right) \quad (21\text{a})$$

Here, k_n and K_n are the forward rate and equilibrium constants of homogeneous reaction n , respectively, $v_{j,n}$ is the stoichiometric coefficient of species j in reaction n ($v_{j,n} < 0$ for reactants of the forward reaction and $v_{j,n} > 0$ for products of the forward reaction), and C_j is the molar concentration of species j .

As an example, when water is in excess, the source term of homogeneous reaction for OH⁻ is equal to [59]

$$S_{\text{h,OH}^-} = S_{\text{h}}^{\text{w}} - S_{\text{h}}^3 - S_{\text{h}}^4 \quad (21\text{b})$$

where

$$S_{\text{h}}^{\text{w}} = k_5 \left(1 - \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{OH}^-}}{K_5} \right) \quad (21\text{c})$$

$$S_{\text{h}}^3 = k_3 \left(C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}} C_{\text{OH}^-} - \frac{C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}{K_3} \right) \quad (21\text{d})$$

$$S_{\text{h}}^4 = k_4 \left(C_{\text{HCO}_3^-} C_{\text{OH}^-} - \frac{C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}{K_4} \right) \quad (21\text{e})$$

2.4.3. Phase change, sorption/desorption and dissolution

The source term of phase change of water is driven by the difference between the partial pressure of water vapor and the saturation pressure of water, $S_{\text{vs}} \propto (p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}})$, so that

$$S_{\text{vs}} = \begin{cases} \frac{\gamma_e}{RT} (p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}), & p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} < p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}} \quad (\text{evaporation}) \\ \frac{\gamma_c}{RT} (p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}), & p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \geq p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}} \quad (\text{condensation}) \end{cases} \quad (22\text{a})$$

where γ_e and γ_c are the evaporation and condensation rate coefficients, given by [73]

$$\gamma_e = k_e a_{\text{lg}} s_{\text{red}} \quad (22\text{b})$$

$$\gamma_c = k_c a_{\text{lg}} (1 - s_{\text{red}}) \quad (22\text{c})$$

In this expression, a_{lg} is the (effective) liquid–gas interfacial area per unit volume, and k_e and k_c are the Hertz–Knudsen mass transfer coefficients [73]

$$k_{e/c} = k_{e/c}^{\text{ref}} \sqrt{\frac{RT}{2\pi M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}}, \quad (22\text{d})$$

with $k_{e/c}^{\text{ref}}$ the reference evaporation/condensation mass transfer coefficient (see the Supplementary Information).

The water sorption/desorption source term is driven by the difference between the equilibrium water content of the sorption isotherm of the electrolyte and the actual water content, $S_{\text{v}\lambda} \propto (\lambda_{\text{eq}} - \lambda)$, so that [59]

$$S_{\text{v}\lambda} = \begin{cases} \frac{k_s}{\delta_{\text{cl}}^{\text{ref}} V_{\text{m}}} (\lambda_{\text{eq}} - \lambda), & \lambda < \lambda_{\text{eq}} \quad (\text{sorption}) \\ \frac{k_d}{\delta_{\text{cl}}^{\text{ref}} V_{\text{m}}} (\lambda_{\text{eq}} - \lambda), & \lambda > \lambda_{\text{eq}} \quad (\text{desorption}) \end{cases} \quad (23\text{a})$$

where $\delta_{\text{cl}}^{\text{ref}}$ is the reference CL thickness, and k_s and k_d are the sorption/desorption mass transfer coefficients, which depend on the volume fraction of water and temperature [73]

$$k_{s/d} = k_{s/d}^{\text{ref}} f_v \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{sd}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (23\text{b})$$

Here, $k_{s/d}^{\text{ref}}$ is the reference sorption/desorption mass transfer coefficient, and E_{sd} is the activation energy of the sorption/desorption process.

The dissolution/desorption rate of CO₂ into/from the CL electrolyte is driven by the difference between the equilibrium and the actual CO₂ concentrations, $S_{\text{d,CO}_2} \propto (C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq,eq}} - C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}})$, taking the following form [41–43,46]

$$S_{\text{d,CO}_2} = a_{\text{a/c}}(1-s) \frac{D_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eff}}}{\delta_{\text{m,cl}} + r_p (1 - \sqrt{1-s})} (C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq,eq}} - C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}) \quad (24\text{a})$$

where $a_{\text{a/c}}(1-s)$ is the available gas specific surface area, and $\delta_{\text{m,cl}}$ and $\delta_{\text{s,cl}} \simeq r_p(1 - \sqrt{1-s})$ are the (average) thicknesses of ionomer and water films in the CL, respectively [42].

The equilibrium CO₂ concentration is determined from Henry's constant, H_{CO_2} , which decreases exponentially with temperature [46]

$$C_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq,eq}} = \frac{x_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{g}}}{p_{\text{atm}}} H_{\text{CO}_2}; \quad H_{\text{CO}_2} [\text{mol m}^{-3}] = 34 \exp \left[-\frac{E_{\text{CO}_2,\text{d}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (24\text{b})$$

where p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure.

2.4.4. Heat

The source/sink heat generation terms in the energy equation arise from four contributions: (i) Joule heating caused by electron and ionic conduction, (ii) latent heat due to water phase change, (iii) reversible and irreversible heat generation by electrochemical reactions, and (iv) heat generation by homogeneous reactions [41,46].

Table 2

Boundary conditions of the system of conservation Eqs. (1a)–(1i) at each boundary of the computational domain. The boundaries where an equation is not solved are indicated by a hyphen.

Equation	abpp/aptl	aptl/acl	acl/aem	aem/ccl	ccl/cmpl	cmpl/cgdl	cgdl/cbpp
ϕ_e	V_{cell}	Continuity	No flux	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0
ϕ_e	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	No flux	–	–
λ	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	No flux	–	–
T	T_{op}	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	T_{op}
p_l	1 atm	Continuity	No flux	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	$p_{\text{op}} + p_c^c$
p_g	1 atm + p_c^a	Continuity	No flux	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	p_{op}
C_{OH^-}	$\frac{C_{\text{KOH}}}{K_w}$	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	No flux	–	–
C_{H^+}	$\frac{C_{\text{KOH}}}{K_w}$	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	No flux	–	–
$C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$	0	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	0
$C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$	0	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	0
C_{HCOO^-}	0	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	Continuity	0
$C_{\text{CO}_2^a}$	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	No flux	–	–
$C_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$	–	–	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0
$C_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$	–	–	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0
C_{HCOOH}	–	–	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0
$x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}}{p_g^a}$	Continuity	No flux	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	$\text{RH}_{\text{op}} \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sat}}}{p_g^c}$
x_{CO_2}	0	Continuity	No flux	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	$1 - x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^c$
x_{CO}	–	–	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0
$x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$	–	–	–	No flux	Continuity	Continuity	0

Joule heating in the 1D model can be expressed as [59]

$$S_{T,\ell} = \sigma_{\ell}^{\text{eff}} \left(\frac{d\phi_{\ell}}{dx} \right)^2; \quad S_{T,e} = \sigma_e^{\text{eff}} \left(\frac{d\phi_e}{dx} \right)^2 \quad (25)$$

where $d\phi_{\ell}/dx$ and $d\phi_e/dx$ are the local derivatives of the ionic and electronic potentials, respectively.

The latent heat of water phase change (evaporation/condensation and sorption/desorption) is equal to [61]

$$S_{T,vs} = h_{\text{lg}} S_{vs}; \quad S_{T,v\lambda} = h_{\text{lg}} S_{v\lambda} \quad (26)$$

where h_{lg} is the specific latent heat of water evaporation/condensation (assumed to be equal to that of water sorption/desorption into/from the ionomer).

The irreversible heat generated under conditions other than equilibrium (i.e., proportional to the overpotential) and the Peltier heat of electrochemical reaction i are given by [46]

$$S_{T,\text{ct}} = \sum_{i=1}^N i_i (|\eta_i| + \Pi_i) \quad (27)$$

where Π_i is the Peltier coefficient of reaction i .

The heat source term of homogeneous reaction n is proportional to the reaction rate [46]

$$S_{T,h} = \sum_n \Delta H_n \left(k_n \Pi_{v_j,n}^{-} C_j^{-v_j,n} - \frac{k_n}{K_n} \Pi_{v_j,n}^{>0} C_j^{v_j,n} \right) \quad (28)$$

where ΔH_n is the enthalpy change.

The energy source terms in the anode and cathode CLs are equal to the sum of all the contributions

$$S_{T,\text{cl}} = S_{T,\ell} + S_{T,e} + S_{T,vs} + S_{T,v\lambda} + S_{T,\text{ct}} + S_{T,h} \quad (29)$$

2.5. Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions imposed on the system of conservation Eqs. (1a)–(1i) at each interface of the computational domain are listed in Table 2. The interfaces where a variable is not solved are marked by a hyphen.

External Dirichlet boundary conditions are prescribed at both the anode abpp/aptl and cathode cgdl/cbpp interfaces for the electronic potential, ϕ_e , temperature, T , liquid- and gas-phase pressures, p_l and p_g , bicarbonate, carbonate and formate concentrations, $C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$, $C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$ and C_{HCOO^-} , and water vapor and gaseous carbon dioxide mole fractions,

$x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and x_{CO_2} . The electronic potential is set equal to the operating voltage, V_{cell} , at the anode terminal, considering a zero potential at the cathode terminal. The temperature in both compartments is fixed to the operating temperature, $T_a = T_c = T_{\text{op}}$. The liquid-phase pressure at the anode is equal to the atmospheric pressure, $p_l^a = p_{\text{atm}}$, while the gas-phase pressure at the cathode is specified according to the operating pressure, $p_g^c = p_{\text{op}}$. The gas-phase pressure at the anode and the liquid-phase pressure at the cathode are determined by considering an interfacial capillary pressure to make the interfacial volume fraction of the secondary phase representative of common operating conditions (gas at the anode and liquid water at the cathode). The capillary pressure at the anode interface is fixed at $p_c^a = 6.5$ kPa ($s_g^a \approx 0.2$), while the capillary pressure at the cathode interface is modified in the study to adapt to the flooding level of the cathode compartment. The bicarbonate, carbonate and formate concentrations are set equal to zero, assuming a high removal rate in the flow fields. The water vapor is saturated by the aqueous solution at the anode and varies depending on the operating relative humidity at the cathode. The mole fraction of gaseous CO_2 is fixed at zero at the anode, considering a fast removal rate of crossover CO_2 , while it is determined to be $x_{\text{CO}_2}^c = 1 - x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^c$ at the cathode.

An external Dirichlet boundary condition on only one cell compartment is prescribed for the hydroxide and proton concentrations, C_{OH^-} and C_{H^+} , ethanol, propanol and formic acid concentrations, $C_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$, $C_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$ and C_{HCOOH} , and carbon monoxide and ethylene mole fractions, x_{CO} and $x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$. The anode hydroxide concentration is set equal to the concentration of the KOH solution, C_{KOH} , due to the complete dissociation of the strong basic solution, while the cathode proton concentration is given by the equilibrium dissociation of water. For both variables, no flux is specified at the ccl/mpl interface, considering that the flux transported to the cathode is negligible. As for ethanol, propanol, and formic acid concentrations, the cathode concentration is fixed at zero due to fast removal in the flow field, while no flux is set at the aem/ccl interface, assuming that crossover is negligible. The same situation holds for gaseous carbon dioxide and ethylene concentrations.

No external boundary conditions are used for the ionic potential, ϕ_{ℓ} , electrolyte water content, λ , and aqueous CO_2 concentration, $C_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}$. At the actl/acl and ccl/cmpl interfaces, no flux is prescribed for these three variables since they are defined in the ionomer phase and do not transport outside the AEM+CLs domain. At the remaining internal boundary conditions not explicitly mentioned above, flux and scalar continuity are prescribed.

2.6. Numerical implementation

The model was numerically implemented in Matlab using the standard boundary value problem solver, `bvp4c`. This finite difference algorithm is based on the three-stage Lobatto IIIa collocation polynomial method, which provides a continuously differentiable solution that is fourth-order accurate uniformly in the computational domain. For the implementation, the system of nineteen second-order ODEs (1a)–(1i) was decomposed into a system of thirty eight first-order ODEs, half for the scalars of interest (ϕ_e , ϕ_ℓ , λ , T , p_l , p_g , C_{OH^-} , C_{H^+} , C_{HCOO^-} , $C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$, $C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$, $C_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}$, $C_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$, $C_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$, C_{HCOOH} , $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, x_{CO_2} , x_{CO} , $x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$), and the other half for the corresponding fluxes (j_{ϕ_e} , j_{ϕ_ℓ} , j_T , j_{p_l} , j_{p_g} , $j_{\text{C}_{\text{OH}^-}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{H}^+}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{HCOO}^-}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}}$, $j_{\text{C}_{\text{HCOOH}}}$, $j_{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}$, $j_{x_{\text{CO}_2}}$, $j_{x_{\text{CO}}}$, $j_{x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}}$) (scalars in $\mathbf{1D}$). The relative and absolute tolerances were set to 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} , respectively, leading to an average computational time of around 1.5 min for a voltage sweep between 2–3.5 V in steps of 50 mV. An example code is provided in the Supplementary Information.

An aspect that deserves further consideration is the sensitivity of the model stability to the conservation equations of hydroxide and protons due to the large variations in pH even when the concentrations of these two species are very small. To deal with this issue, the conservation equations of these two species were re-written in terms of the pOH and pH

$$\text{pOH} = -\log_{10}\left(\frac{C_{\text{OH}^-}}{10^3}\right); \quad \text{pH} = -\log_{10}\left(\frac{C_{\text{H}^+}}{10^3}\right) \quad (30a)$$

so that

$$C_{\text{OH}^-} = 10^{3-\text{pOH}}; \quad \frac{dC_{\text{OH}^-}}{dx} = -\ln(10) C_{\text{OH}^-} \frac{d\text{pOH}}{dx} \quad (30b)$$

and

$$C_{\text{H}^+} = 10^{3-\text{pH}}; \quad \frac{dC_{\text{H}^+}}{dx} = -\ln(10) C_{\text{H}^+} \frac{d\text{pH}}{dx} \quad (30c)$$

Introducing these results, the conservation equation for C_{OH^-} and C_{H^+} takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx} \left(-D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}} \frac{dC_i}{dx} + u_1 C_i - \frac{z_i F D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}}}{RT} C_i \frac{d\phi_\ell}{dx} \right) &= S_{i,l}^c \\ \Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \left(D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}} \ln(10) C_i \frac{d\text{pOH (or pH)}}{dx} + u_1 C_i - \frac{z_i F D_{i,l}^{\text{eff}}}{RT} C_i \frac{d\phi_\ell}{dx} \right) &= S_{i,l}^c \end{aligned} \quad (30d)$$

where $C_i = 10^{3-\text{pOH (or pH)}}$.

This natural change of variable ensures that the hydroxide and proton concentrations are positive, avoiding the potential appearance of slightly negative values during the solution scheme for which pOH/pH is not defined.

2.7. Output variables

Apart from the through-plane profiles of the solution variables, the output parameters considered are: (i) the polarization curve, (ii) the voltage loss breakdown, (iii) the Faradaic efficiency, (iv) the CO_2 and OH^- utilization, and (v) the ethylene production (i.e., partial current density).

For a given cell voltage, the output current density, I , can be directly determined by evaluating the electronic potential flux at the anode abpp/appl interface

$$I = -\sigma_e^{\text{eff}} \frac{d\phi_e}{dx} \Big|_{\text{abpp/appl}} \quad (31)$$

The voltage breakdown is determined using the mean electronic and ionic potentials in the anode and cathode CLs, $\bar{\phi}_{e/\ell,\text{acl}}$ and $\bar{\phi}_{e/\ell,\text{ccl}}$,

together with the average pH correction of the Nernst potentials, $\Delta\bar{U}_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}$ and $\Delta\bar{U}_c^{\text{eq}}$, leading to

$$V_{\text{cell}} = \underbrace{(V_{\text{cell}} - \bar{\phi}_{e,\text{acl}})}_{\Delta\phi_{e,a} + \Delta\phi_{e,c} = \Delta\phi_e} + \underbrace{(\bar{\phi}_{e,\text{acl}} - \bar{\phi}_{e,\text{ccl}})}_{\Delta\phi_\ell} \quad (32a)$$

$$+ \underbrace{(\bar{\phi}_{e,\text{acl}} - \bar{\phi}_{e,\text{acl}} - \{U_{\text{O,OER}} - \Delta\bar{U}_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}\})}_{\eta_a} + \underbrace{(\bar{\phi}_{e,\text{ccl}} - \bar{\phi}_{e,\text{ccl}} - \Delta\bar{U}_c^{\text{eq}})}_{\eta_c} \quad (32b)$$

$$+ \underbrace{(U_{\text{O,OER}} - \Delta\bar{U}_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}})}_{U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}} + \underbrace{(\Delta\bar{U}_c^{\text{eq}})}_{U_c^{\text{eq}}} - \phi_e^0 \quad (32c)$$

where $U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}$ and U_c^{eq} are the corrected anode and cathode equilibrium potentials, respectively. Therefore, $V_{\text{cell}} = U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}} + U_c^{\text{eq}} + \eta_c + \eta_a + \Delta\phi_e + \Delta\phi_\ell$, when the reference voltage is fixed at $\phi_e^0 = 0$.

The Faradaic efficiency or selectivity of product k in the cathode CL is defined as

$$\text{FE}_k = \frac{I_k}{I}; \quad I = \sum_k I_k \quad (33)$$

where I_k is the portion of the current density devoted to the generation of species k ,

$$I_k = \int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} i_k dx, \quad (34)$$

and i_k is the corresponding volumetric current density (see Section 2.4).

The carbon dioxide utilization is quantified as the fraction of CO_2 (aq) flux that is invested in electrochemical reduction compared to the total flux that is dissolved in the hydrated ionomer phase at the cathode

$$U_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}} = -\frac{\int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} S_{\text{ct,CO}_2^{\text{aq}}} dx}{\int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} S_{\text{d,CO}_2} dx} \leq 1 \quad (35a)$$

Similarly, the CO_2 utilization including also the amount lost by carbonation is equal to

$$U_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}^{\text{ct+h}} = -\frac{\int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} S_{\text{d,CO}_2} dx - \int_0^{\delta_{\text{acl}}} S_{\text{d,CO}_2} dx}{\int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} S_{\text{d,CO}_2} dx} \leq 1 \quad (35b)$$

where the second term in the numerator is the flux of CO_2 (aq) desorbed at the anode.

The hydroxide utilization at the anode is defined as

$$U_{\text{OH}^-} = \frac{\int_0^{\delta_{\text{acl}}} \frac{i_{\text{OER}}^{\text{alk}}}{F} dx}{N_{\text{OH}^-}^{\text{in,a}} + \int_0^{\delta_{\text{ccl}}} S_{\text{ct,OH}^-}^c dx} \leq 1 \quad (35c)$$

where the numerator represents the consumption rate in the anode CL, and the denominator is equal to the sum of the inlet flux at the abpp/appl interface plus the generation flux in the cathode CL.

The ethylene production rate can be simply examined through the corresponding partial current density

$$I_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4} = I \text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4} \quad (36)$$

where I and $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ are given by Eqs. (31) and (33), respectively.

3. Case studies

Table 3 gathers all the operating scenarios analyzed in the discussion of results (Section 4), allowing the reader to identify at a glance which conditions are varied in each section and how they relate to the corresponding figures. The case studies are designed to track, variable by variable, how operating conditions reshape kinetics, transport, water management, and carbonate chemistry in a zero-gap CO_2 electrolyzer. All scenarios inherit the boundary-condition framework of Table 2: cell voltage imposed at the anode, equal operating temperature on both sides, cathode gas pressure set to the operating

Table 3

Case studies examined in the discussion of results. The interfacial liquid saturation at the cgd/ cbpp interface is indicated between brackets in the cathode capillary pressure column. The footnote indicates the electrochemical parameters adopted in each case for a better agreement with experimental data.

Section	Temperature °C	RH	Cathode capillary pressure kPa	KOH concentration M	Operating pressure bar	Drag factor –
4.1 ^a	25	1	0 (0.2)	1	1	2
4.2 ^{b,c}	30–70	1	0 (0.2)	1	1	2
4.3 ^d	25	0.3,1	–2 (0.05)	1	1	2
4.4 ^e	25	1	0 (0.2)	0.05–10	1	2
4.5 ^f	25	1	0 (0.2)	1	0–20	2
4.6.1 ^g	20–70	1	0 (0.2)	1,5	0.5–8	2
4.6.2 ^g	25	0.3–1	0–1.82 (0.2–0.4)	1,5	1	–5–8

^a The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

^b The anode and cathode specific surface areas are varied to $a_a = a_c = 5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$.

^c The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 9 \times 10^{-9} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

^d The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 3.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

^e The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

^f The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 3.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 5.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 7.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 3.25 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

^g The reference exchange current densities of the anode are varied to $i_{0,HER}^{ref} = 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,CO}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,HCOO}^{ref} = 4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_4} = 6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, $i_{0,C_2H_5OH}^{ref} = 7 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$, and $i_{0,C_3H_7OH}^{ref} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ A m}^{-2}$.

pressure, prescribed interfacial capillary pressures to represent typical secondary-phase fractions, anode C_{KOH} fixed by the anolyte solution, and cathode relative humidity. Unless otherwise noted via the footnotes in Table 3 (a)–(g), transport, thermodynamic, and kinetic parameters are those reported in the Supplementary Information. Small, literature-consistent adjustments to selected exchange current densities and/or specific surface areas are applied on a per-series basis solely to align the model magnitude and slope with reference datasets used for validation; the mechanistic interpretations that follow are therefore governed by the constitutive relations rather than these minor prefactor changes. The operating conditions explored in this study (temperature, pressure, inlet relative humidity, and electrolyte composition) were selected to span the range commonly reported for zero-gap AEM-based CO₂ electrolyzers in the literature, ensuring practical relevance while enabling systematic assessment of performance-limiting mechanisms. The technological aspects discussed in each section are presented below:

- **Baseline** (Section 4.1). The reference case anchors the discussion by validating polarization behavior, voltage-loss breakdown, and Faradaic efficiency under conventional operation: 25 °C, fully humidified cathode feed (RH_{op} = 1), $p_{op} = 1$ bar cathode pressure, no imposed cathode capillary pressure ($p_c^c = 0$ Pa, $s^c \approx 0.2$), $C_{KOH} = 1$ M KOH anolyte, and an effective drag factor $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$. Minor parameter tweaks listed in footnote (a) of Table 3 are used for agreement with the experimental trends reviewed in Section 4.1.
- **Single-parameter sweeps** (Sections 4.2–4.5). Four orthogonal series are used to deconvolute individual levers:

1. **Temperature**: $T_{op} = 30\text{--}70$ °C (Section 4.2). At RH_{op} = 1, $p_{op} = 1$ bar, no cathode capillary pressure ($p_c^c = 0$ Pa, $s^c \approx 0.2$), $C_{KOH} = 1$ M KOH, and $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$; the specific surface areas $a_a = a_c$ are set to $5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and the reference exchange current densities follow footnotes (b)–(c) of Table 3. This sweep shows how faster kinetics and ohmic transport compete with reduced CO₂ solubility as temperature rises.
2. **Relative humidity**: RH_{op} = 0.3,1 (Section 4.3). At $T_{op} = 25$ °C, $p_{op} = 1$ bar, $p_c^c = -2$ kPa ($s^c \approx 0.05$), $C_{KOH} = 1$ M KOH, and $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$. Reference exchange current densities are adapted to footnote (d) of Table 3. This

series clarifies how hydration lowers ionic losses up to the flooding threshold, beyond which gaseous CO₂ transport is impaired.

3. **Anolyte concentration**: $C_{KOH} = 0.05\text{--}10$ M (Section 4.4). At $T_{op} = 25$ °C, RH_{op} = 1, $p_{op} = 1$ bar, no cathode capillary pressure ($p_c^c = 0$ Pa, $s^c \approx 0.2$), and $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$, with Table 3 footnote (e) adjustments. This section quantifies the bifunctional role of pH and hydroxide inventory-suppressing HER yet risking excessive carbonation.
 4. **Cathode pressure**: $p_{op} = 0\text{--}20$ bar (Section 4.5). At $T_{op} = 25$ °C, RH_{op} = 1, $C_{KOH} = 1$ M KOH, no cathode capillary pressure ($p_c^c = 0$ Pa, $s^c \approx 0.2$), and $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$, with Table 3 footnote (f) prefactors. The results reveal the pressure window where added CO₂ availability helps operation, and the high-pressure regime where carbonation and catalytic pathway shifts undermine performance; a focused $p_{op} = 0\text{--}2$ bar subset provides practical resolution.
- **Coupled operational maps** (Section 4.6). Two two-dimensional studies locate the operable windows where multiple mechanisms balance:
 1. **Temperature–pressure maps** ($T_{op} = 20\text{--}70$ °C \times $p_{op} = 0.5\text{--}8$ bar) (Section 4.6.1). It is computed at RH_{op} = 1, no cathode capillary pressure ($p_c^c = 0$ Pa, $s^c \approx 0.2$) and $f_{eod}^{eff} = 2$, for $C_{KOH} = 1$ M and 5 M KOH (see footnote (g) in Table 3 for other adjustments). This section shows the diagonal ridge where pressure compensates thermal solubility losses, explains why the FE optimum differs from the current density optimum, and highlights how a higher KOH reservoir raises carbonation risk.
 2. **Relative humidity–water drag maps** (RH_{op} = 0.3 – 1 \times $f_{eod}^{eff} = -5\text{--}8$) (Section 4.6.2). It is computed at $T_{op} = 25$ °C and $p_{op} = 1$ bar for $C_{KOH} = 1$ M and 5 M KOH, with the cathode interfacial capillary pressure varied between $p_c^c = 0\text{--}1.82$ kPa ($s^c \approx 0.2\text{--}0.4$) to modify the gas–liquid boundary condition at the ccl/cmpl interface when RH_{op} = 1 (see footnote (g) in Table 3 for other adjustments). This section demonstrates that performance is maximized at good cathode humidification and moderate effective anode–cathode drag (typically $f_{eod}^{eff} \approx 0\text{--}2$), where the cathode is hydrated

Fig. 2. Comparison of representative results of the numerical model against previous experimental data at the baseline conditions. (a) Polarization curve compared to the data of Lee et al. [74], Larrazabal et al. [20], Ertugrul et al. [46] and Giron-Rodríguez et al. [26]. (b) Voltage breakdown for the case in (a), indicating the contributions of the corrected anode and cathode equilibrium potentials, $U_{\text{OER}}^{\text{eq}}$ and U_{c}^{eq} , anode and cathode overpotentials, η_{a} and η_{c} , ionic transport, $\Delta\phi_{\ell}$, and electronic transport, $\Delta\phi_{\text{e}}$. (c) Faradaic efficiency as a function of current density reported in several experimental studies for the main CO₂RR products in alkaline media [25,46,71,75,76]. (d) Predicted breakdown of the Faradaic efficiency by the numerical model.

yet unflooded, CO₂ access is preserved, CO₂ utilization remains high, and HER is minimized.

Together, these cases give the reader a clear roadmap of the effect of operating conditions and flooding in CO₂ electrolyzers. The baseline case establishes the reference behavior and carbon/hydroxide fates; the single-parameter sweeps isolate the roles of temperature, humidity, pH/anolyte concentration, and pressure; and the coupled maps quantify the narrow but actionable windows where kinetics/ohmic losses, CO₂ solubility, water management, and carbonate chemistry align to maximize ethylene productivity without incurring severe ionic or carbon-efficiency penalties.

4. Discussion of results

4.1. Baseline case

Model validation was performed by comparison with representative experimental data reported in the literature under comparable operating conditions, including polarization behavior, voltage-loss

distribution, and product selectivity. Fig. 2 presents this validation in detail, showing that the model accurately reproduces polarization curves, voltage-loss breakdown, and product selectivity under conventional conditions. The agreement across these independent metrics demonstrates that the model successfully captures the dominant electrochemical and transport processes governing CO₂RR in zero-gap MEA electrolyzers, including the coupled effects of transport, reaction kinetics, and carbonate chemistry.

The polarization curve in Fig. 2(a) shows overall good agreement with representative experimental data from several studies on Cu-based MEA systems [20,26,46,74]. The discrepancy is larger at low overpotentials, where the model slightly underpredicts the current density relative to experiments. This deviation is expected because the present formulation uses Tafel kinetics for all electrode reactions, which is appropriate at high overpotentials but does not fully recover Butler-Volmer symmetry in the near-equilibrium regime. As a result, the model underestimates the activation-controlled region while reproducing the experimentally observed slope with high fidelity once the cell enters the kinetically relevant high-overpotential regime. Similar behavior has been discussed in prior modeling analyses of MEA-based

CO₂ electrolyzers, where Tafel kinetics adequately describe performance under industrially relevant current densities (see, e.g., [41,43–45]). The voltage breakdown displayed in Fig. 2(b) further confirms the predictive capabilities of the model. The largest contributions to the total cell voltage stem from the cathode overpotential and the ionic voltage drop across the AEM and CL (comparable to the anode overpotential), with a smaller contribution from the electronic voltage drop. This trend is fully consistent with experimental observations and previous modeling efforts, which emphasize that multicarbon formation on Cu requires a substantial cathodic driving force and that ionic transport limitations dominate at high current densities [25, 26,41,77,78]. The Faradaic efficiency results in Fig. 2(c)–(d) further validate the model's predictive capacity. Consistent with extensive experimental evidence [25,46,71,75,76], the simulations show that C₂⁺ products, especially ethylene, become increasingly favored at high cathode overpotentials (current densities), where elevated CO coverage and intensified C–C coupling promote ethylene formation [18–20]. Conversely, C₁ products such as CO and formate decrease in relative contribution at higher current densities. The model also captures the experimentally observed increase in hydrogen evolution at high currents, which is driven by enhanced cathode flooding that impedes CO₂ transport, agreeing with operando and modeling studies linking water accumulation to HER surges and selectivity deterioration [15,71,79]. Notably, the comparison with Faradaic efficiencies reported by multiple independent experimental groups shows remarkably good agreement, confirming that the model reproduces both qualitative and quantitative selectivity trends across the full range of operating conditions.

Fig. 3 provides key insights into the fate of CO₂ and OH[−] within the MEA under baseline conditions, highlighting the strong influence of carbonation chemistry on device performance [80,81]. A central observation from Fig. 3(a) is the large fraction of CO₂ that is lost to parasitic carbonation reactions, particularly at low and intermediate current densities. In this regime, the rate of CO₂RR in the cathode CL is moderate, while the local hydroxide concentration is high, favoring rapid formation of (bi)carbonate through neutralization reactions (Reactions (20a)–(20e)). As a result, only a limited proportion of the dissolved CO₂ is converted into useful products, with most of it instead undergoing carbonation. This trend is well aligned with previous experimental and modeling studies, which have consistently reported substantial carbon losses due to (bi)carbonate formation in AEM-based CO₂ electrolyzers [15,41]. As the current density (and thus cell voltage) increases, the electrochemical consumption of CO₂ becomes higher, reducing the fraction available for carbonation and leading to improved CO₂ utilization. A similar conclusion applies to hydroxide consumption, as also shown in Fig. 3(a). A significant portion of OH[−] generated at the cathode, either through the HER or CO₂RR, is consumed by carbonation reactions rather than contributing to useful ionic conduction or participating directly in electrochemical pathways. This behavior is consistent with mechanistic insights describing how carbonate formation drains hydroxide from the electrolyte, thereby affecting pH regulation and ionic conductivity [32,33]. As shown in Fig. 3(b), the aqueous CO₂ concentration decreases sharply across the AEM, reaching very low values at the anode side, consistent with strong carbonation-driven depletion in the membrane region. Moreover, as the current density increases, the rate of CO₂RR increases proportionally, further lowering the CO₂ concentration within the cathode CL. This behavior aligns with the well-established depletion of CO₂ at high reaction rates reported in MEA studies (see, e.g., [25,26]).

Fig. 3(c)–(d) shows the corresponding distributions of bicarbonate and carbonate concentrations across the MEA. These results reveal that the formation of HCO₃[−] and CO₃^{2−} is particularly pronounced at low current densities, where a high supply of dissolved CO₂ coexists with abundant OH[−]. Under these conditions, most dissolved inorganic carbon shifts toward carbonate species. At higher current densities, the situation becomes somewhat alleviated on the cathode side because the elevated electrochemical CO₂ consumption leaves less CO₂ available

for carbonation. This is consistent with previously reported analyses showing that carbon speciation is strongly controlled by the balance between electrochemical consumption and parasitic neutralization reactions [41,70]. The model outcomes highlight the performance penalties associated with carbonation, a phenomenon widely documented in the literature. Carbonate formation reduces ionic conductivity within the AEM, alters local pH, and promotes salt precipitation, particularly as carbonate species accumulate and crystallize within the porous cathode GDE [15,33]. Such precipitation can obstruct pores, impair CO₂ transport, induce cathode flooding, and ultimately lead to operational instability, issues that have been clearly observed in operando imaging and durability studies (see, e.g., [28,35] among others). While the present model already captures carbonation chemistry with good fidelity, the results in Fig. 3 suggest that future extensions should incorporate precipitation kinetics and solid-phase transport phenomena to fully reproduce the evolution of carbonate-induced degradation.

4.2. Effect of operating temperature

Fig. 4 examines the influence of operating temperature on the electrochemical performance and microenvironment of the zero-gap CO₂ electrolyzer. A key observation from Fig. 4(a) is that increasing temperature strongly decreases the CO₂ solubility, owing to the exponential decrease in Henry's constant with temperature (Eq. (24b)), which leads to significantly lower aqueous CO₂ concentrations in the cathode CL [82]. Conversely, the HER rate is comparatively insensitive to CO₂ availability, and thus HER is not directly hindered by the drop in CO₂ solubility. As a result, HER selectivity increases with temperature relative to CO₂RR, a trend that is consistent with experimental observations on Cu-based GDEs [25,26]. Despite this shift in selectivity, the cell performance improves with increasing temperature, as evidenced by the polarization curves in Fig. 4(b). This performance enhancement arises from two dominant temperature-driven effects: (i) the promotion of electrochemical kinetics, captured in the exponential temperature dependence of all exchange current densities (Supplementary Information), and (ii) the reduction of ionic transport losses due to the increase in ionic conductivity and water diffusion within the electrolyte phase (Eqs. (14a)–(14e)) [83]. The voltage breakdown analysis in Fig. 4(c) further clarifies the origin of these improvements. At moderate to high current densities ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$), the most pronounced change with temperature is the decrease in the ionic voltage drop, while the anode and cathode overpotentials remain nearly unchanged. This indicates that ionic transport within the AEM and CLs is the primary bottleneck relieved by increasing temperature. The inset in Fig. 4(c), focused on low current density ($I \approx 0.01 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$), reveals that both anodic and cathodic overpotentials decrease with temperature in the activation-controlled regime, reflecting the enhancement of kinetic parameters (i.e., exchange current density). Fig. 4(d) provides additional mechanistic insight by examining the temperature dependence of the average pH in the anode CL and the concentration of dissolved CO₂ in the cathode CL. The results show that the pH remains relatively stable, taking values between 12 and 13 across the full temperature range of 30–70 °C. This behavior arises from the buffering action of carbonate species and the balance between OH[−] generation (HER and CO₂RR) and consumption (carbonation reactions), which remain nearly constant with temperature. In contrast, the aqueous CO₂ concentration decreases sharply with temperature, driven by the steep decline in Henry's constant commented earlier.

4.3. Effect of operating relative humidity

Fig. 5 evaluates the effect of cathode RH on the performance, voltage characteristics, and local microenvironment of the zero-gap CO₂ electrolyzer. The results demonstrate that the model accurately

Fig. 3. Variation of CO_2 and OH^- utilizations, $U_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}$ and U_{OH^-} , as a function of current density for the baseline case. (b) Through-plane distributions of aqueous CO_2 across the AEM+CLs region at different voltages, $V_{\text{cell}} = 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5 \text{ V}$. (c)–(d) Through-plane distributions of bicarbonate and carbonate concentrations, $C_{\text{HCO}_3^-}$ and $C_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}$, across the MEA at different V_{cell} . The location of the AEM and the CLs is indicated by a gray background, and the ccl/cmpl interface is indicated by a dashed line.

captures the well-documented sensitivity of CO_2 reduction to humidification conditions, particularly the subtle balance between water availability, flooding, ionic conductivity, and CO_2 transport limitations [84, 85].

A central observation from Fig. 5(a) is that CO_2 reduction is promoted in wet cathode environments, provided that the level of flooding remains moderate. Under sufficiently humid conditions, greater water availability enhances electrolyte hydration and stabilizes the interfacial environment, suppressing HER relative to CO_2RR and thus improving multicarbon selectivity. This is consistent with recent operando and modeling studies that show that humidified feeds support CO_2RR activity by improving ionic mobility within the ionomer phase while avoiding severe water accumulation [41,71]. However, this beneficial effect only holds if flooding does not become extensive enough to obstruct gaseous CO_2 transport, a well-known failure mode in Cu-based GDEs [15,86,87]. Fig. 5(b) reveals that overall performance increases in wet environments, as evidenced by the lower cell voltages attained at a given current density. This enhancement stems primarily from improvements in ohmic transport within the electrolyte, given that water uptake in the ionomer increases its ionic conductivity (Eq. (14a)–(14e))

and reduces the resistance associated with hydroxide migration across the AEM. These findings are in agreement with earlier MEA studies where humidification improved ionic conductivity and reduced cell voltage penalties [4,43]. The voltage breakdown in Fig. 5(c) provides deeper insight. Under moderately wet conditions, the ionic voltage drop decreases significantly, while the anode and cathode overpotentials remain nearly unchanged over most of the current-density range. This indicates that the primary benefit of humidification arises from decreased electrolyte resistance rather than from accelerated charge-transfer kinetics, which are relatively insensitive to RH. Only at low current densities, where activation control dominates, do the overpotentials show visible reductions with increased humidity, which is consistent with improved ionomer hydration and reduced local pH gradients in the activation regime. These trends mirror documented behavior in alkaline MEAs, where water uptake in the solid electrolyte phase governs the ionic transport penalty [6,26]. Fig. 5(d) shows the variation of the cathode CL humidity and saturation. As can be seen in the red curves, no water is present at the cathode in the dry-feed case, thus leading to suboptimal cathode hydration. In contrast, the blue curves, corresponding to the wet-feed case, demonstrate that the

Fig. 4. (a) Comparison of the predicted Faradaic efficiency as a function of the operating temperature, T_{op} , against the experimental data of Ren et al. [25] ($I \approx 0.15$ A cm $^{-2}$). (b) Comparison of the predicted polarization curves at $T_{op} = 30$ °C and $T_{op} = 70$ °C against the experimental data of Giron-Rodríguez et al. [26]. (c) Variation of the anode and cathode overpotentials, η_a and η_c , and ionic voltage drop, $\Delta\phi_\ell$, as a function of T_{op} ($I \approx 0.15$ A cm $^{-2}$). The inset shows the variation of the anode and cathode overpotentials at low current density ($I \approx 0.01$ A cm $^{-2}$). (d) Variation of (left) the average pH of the anode CL, pH_{acl} , and (right) the average aqueous CO_2^{aq} concentration in the cathode CL, $C_{CO_2^{aq},ccl}$, as a function of T_{op} ($I \approx 0.15$ A cm $^{-2}$).

cathode CL remains in a state of moderate saturation, well below the conditions that would trigger catastrophic flooding. This aligns with experimental reports showing that controlled humidification can maintain a stable reaction zone without fully saturating the GDE structure [36,37]. The model therefore accurately captures the competing effects of water availability and capillary transport within the CL, reinforcing the physical validity of the two-phase formulation.

4.4. Effect of operating pH

Figure 6 illustrates the effect of the anolyte concentration, C_{KOH} , on the electrochemical performance, selectivity, and carbonate chemistry of the zero-gap alkaline CO_2 electrolyzer. Increasing KOH concentration strengthens the alkaline character of the MEA, affecting ionic transport, HER suppression, and carbonation behavior. At low KOH concentration, hydroxide availability is insufficient to sustain high ionic conduction through the AEM and CLs. Consequently, ohmic losses increase and HER becomes more competitive due to the weaker alkaline microenvironment, resulting in lower current density and reduced C_2H_4

selectivity. In addition, the limited OH^- flux toward the anode increases the anodic overpotential because the hydroxide concentration near the anode CL decreases at high current density, hindering efficient OER operation. As shown in Figure 6(a)–(b), increasing C_{KOH} improves both polarization behavior and ethylene Faradaic efficiency because the enhanced OH^- reservoir facilitates ionic transport and suppresses HER kinetics [41–43]. This behavior is consistent with previous experimental observations in alkaline MEAs [22,30–33]. However, excessive alkalinity progressively intensifies carbonation reactions, converting a larger fraction of dissolved CO_2 into (bi)carbonate species. As illustrated in Figure 6(c)–(d), this enhanced carbonation lowers effective CO_2 utilization and gradually reduces the availability of CO_2 at the cathode CL. Although ionic losses remain low at high KOH concentration, the cathode microenvironment becomes increasingly dominated by carbonate transport rather than productive CO_2 reduction. The voltage-loss breakdown in Figure 6(c) clarifies this trade-off. Dilute KOH operation is limited primarily by ionic and kinetic losses, including the rise in anodic overpotential associated with the reduction of OH^- concentration near the anode, whereas concentrated KOH

Fig. 5. (a) Comparison of the predicted Faradaic efficiency for dry ($\text{RH}_{\text{op}} = 0.3$) and wet ($\text{RH}_{\text{op}} = 1$) cathode feed against the experimental data of Fu et al. [71] ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (b) Polarization curve comparison for the dry and wet cases. (c) Variation of the predicted anode and cathode overpotentials, η_a and η_c , and ionic voltage drop, $\Delta\phi_\ell$, as a function of the current density for the dry and wet cases ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (d) Variation of (left) the average RH, RH_{ccl} , and (right) the average liquid saturation, $s_{\text{ccl}} - s_r$, in the cathode CL as a function of the current density for the dry and wet cases ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$).

operation is increasingly affected by carbonate-mediated CO_2 depletion. Therefore, the best performance emerges at intermediate KOH concentrations, where hydroxide availability is sufficient to maintain low ohmic resistance and suppress HER without excessively scavenging CO_2 through carbonation. These results reinforce the central conclusion of this work: high ethylene selectivity requires a balanced local microenvironment in which ionic conduction, CO_2 accessibility, and carbonate chemistry remain simultaneously optimized.

4.5. Effect of operating pressure

Fig. 7 examines the effect of cathode operating pressure, p_{op} , on the selectivity and electrochemical performance of the zero-gap alkaline CO_2 electrolyzer. Increasing pressure enhances CO_2 availability in the cathode compartment by increasing dissolved CO_2 concentration according to Henry's law. As a result, moderate pressurization initially improves CO_2RR activity and promotes C-C coupling, leading to higher C_2H_4 selectivity, as shown in Fig. 7(a)–(b). This trend agrees with experimental observations reported by Huang et al. [29] and Girichandran et al. [28], where moderate cathode pressurization increased ethylene production in Cu-based MEAs. The beneficial effect

of pressure is most evident at low-to-intermediate pressures, where the larger dissolved CO_2 concentration enhances CO surface coverage while maintaining a sufficiently alkaline microenvironment for C-C coupling. Under these conditions, polarization behavior remains nearly unchanged, as shown in Fig. 7(d), indicating that moderate pressure improves reactant availability without significantly increasing transport penalties or carbonate accumulation. This behavior suggests that, within this regime, the gain in CO_2 accessibility outweighs the additional carbonation induced by the higher dissolved CO_2 concentration. However, as pressure continues to increase, carbonation effects become progressively more important. The larger amount of dissolved CO_2 accelerates carbonation reactions, converting a growing fraction of CO_2 into (bi)carbonate species. This enhanced carbonation progressively consumes OH^- and reduces its concentration near the anode CL, thereby increasing the anodic overpotential required to sustain the OER. Consequently, the cell voltage rises at elevated pressure, particularly for diluted KOH operation, as observed in Fig. 7(c). The increasing carbonate inventory also modifies the cathode reaction environment. While moderate pressure favors CO-mediated C-C coupling, excessive CO_2 chemical potential progressively shifts the selectivity toward formate production, reducing the fraction of carbon directed

Fig. 6. (a) Comparison of the predicted Faradaic efficiency as a function of the average pH in the AEM+CLs region, pH_m , against the experimental data of Dauda et al. [70] ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (b) Polarization curves corresponding to four pHs, $\text{pH}_m = 9, 11, 12, 13$. (c) Variation of the anode and cathode overpotentials, η_a and η_c , and the ionic voltage drop, $\Delta\phi_\ell$, as a function of pH_m ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (d) Variation of the normalized CO_2 flux invested in useful reduction reactions at the cathode (utilization), in parasitic carbonation reactions (carbonation) and in crossover to the anode (crossover) as a function of pH_m ($I \approx 0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). The fluxes are normalized with respect to the dissolution rate of CO_2^{aq} in the cathode CL.

toward ethylene. Therefore, the highest pressures do not correspond to the highest C_2H_4 Faradaic efficiencies, despite the improved CO_2 solubility and mass transport.

Fig. 8 extends the pressure analysis introduced in Fig. 7 by providing a mechanistic interpretation of how cathode pressurization affects current density, CO_2 utilization, carbonate chemistry, and voltage losses within the MEA. The figure clarifies that pressure influences the electrolyzer through two competing mechanisms: (i) enhanced CO_2 availability and (ii) intensified carbonation, both of which have been widely reported in alkaline CO_2 electrolyzers [15,29,31,33]. At low-to-moderate pressures, increasing cathode pressure improves CO_2 dissolution and transport to the cathode CL, which enhances the local CO_2 concentration available for electro-reduction. As a result, both current density and CO_2 utilization initially increase, particularly for the 1 M KOH case, where the system is more sensitive to reactant availability. This behavior is consistent with the increase in C_2H_4 selectivity observed previously in Fig. 7(a)–(b), confirming that moderate pressurization promotes CO-mediated C–C coupling by increasing surface CO coverage [28,29]. Similar pressure-induced improvements in CO_2RR

activity have also been observed experimentally in Cu-based MEAs and flow electrolyzers [16,28,29]. As pressure continues to rise, however, the beneficial effect of improved CO_2 transport becomes progressively offset by stronger carbonation reactions. The larger dissolved CO_2 inventory reacts more readily with OH^- through carbonation reactions, increasing the formation and transport of (bi)carbonate species across the membrane. Consequently, a growing fraction of the supplied CO_2 is consumed chemically rather than electrochemically, causing CO_2 utilization to decrease at elevated pressure despite the higher CO_2 solubility. This trend is fully consistent with previous operando and modeling studies identifying carbonation as one of the dominant limitations in alkaline MEA electrolyzers [15,31,41–43,47]. This enhanced carbonation also affects the voltage distribution within the cell. As carbonate formation intensifies, OH^- consumption increases and the hydroxide concentration near the anode CL decreases, which raises the anodic overpotential required to sustain the OER. In addition, the ohmic losses also increase when the OH^- concentration is reduced. Therefore, the increase in cell voltage at high pressure originates primarily from the anode side (and the membrane) rather than from

Fig. 7. (a) Comparison of the predicted Faradaic efficiency as a function of the cathode operating pressure, p_{op} , for 1 M and 5 M KOH against the experimental data of Huang et al. [29] in the range $p_{\text{op}} = 0-20$ bar ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (b) Detailed comparison of the Faradaic efficiency against the experimental data of Giron-Rodríguez et al. [26] in the reduced range $p_{\text{op}} = 0-2$ bar ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (c) Polarization curves corresponding to four operating pressures in the range 0–20 bar, $p_{\text{op}} = 1, 5, 10, 20$ bar, for 1 M and 5 M KOH. (d) Polarization curves corresponding to four operating pressures in the range 0–2 bar, $p_{\text{op}} = 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2$ bar, for 1 M and 5 M KOH.

cathode kinetic limitations. The effect becomes more pronounced for the 1 M KOH case because the smaller hydroxide reservoir is less capable of buffering the pressure-induced increase in carbonation. Similar coupling between carbonation, hydroxide depletion, and increased anodic losses has been discussed previously in alkaline CO_2 electrolysis studies [31,41,43]. At the same time, excessive CO_2 chemical potential modifies the cathode reaction environment and progressively shifts the selectivity toward formate production, as already observed in Fig. 7(a). Under these conditions, the cathode microenvironment becomes increasingly dominated by carbonate transport and local pH variations, which weaken the conditions required for stable C–C coupling and high ethylene selectivity. This pressure-driven shift in selectivity agrees with experimental observations under high CO_2 chemical potential reported by Huang et al. [29]. These results demonstrate that the optimal pressure window emerges from a balance between enhanced CO_2 accessibility and the detrimental effects of carbonation. Moderate pressure improves CO_2RR activity and ethylene formation, whereas excessive pressure increases carbonate formation, lowers effective CO_2 utilization, and raises anodic losses associated with the reduction of local OH^- concentration.

4.6. Parametric study

4.6.1. Coupled effect of operating temperature and pressure

Figs. 9 and 10 together map the coupled effect of operating temperature and cathode pressure on current density, CO_2 utilization, ethylene selectivity, and ethylene production at $V_{\text{cell}} = 3.5$ V. These contour plots represent the first fully coupled visualization in this study of how thermal, mass-transport, and ionic-transport phenomena interact in the zero-gap configuration. They extend and unify the isolated temperature trends discussed in Fig. 4 and the pressure-induced behaviors analyzed in Figs. 7 and 8. The combined maps reveal the intricate, nonlinear interdependencies between CO_2 solubility, CO_2RR kinetics, CO_2 availability, hydroxide transport, and carbonation chemistry. Ethylene is selected as the representative product because it is the most industrially valuable multicarbon product generated on Cu catalysts, representing the dominant techno-economic driver for CO_2 electrolyzer development and the key benchmark for assessing C_2^+ performance in MEA systems.

The current density contours in Fig. 9(a)–(b) show that both temperature and cathode pressure promote higher reaction rates, but through

Fig. 8. (a) Variation of the predicted anode and cathode overpotentials, η_a and η_c , and ionic voltage drop, $\Delta\phi_\ell$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH in the range $p_{\text{op}} = 0-20 \text{ bar}$ ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (b) Variation of η_a , η_c and $\Delta\phi_\ell$ for 1 M and 5 M KOH in the reduced range $p_{\text{op}} = 0-2 \text{ bar}$ ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (c) Variation of (left) the average pH in the anode CL, pH_{acl} , and (right) the average aqueous CO_2 concentration in the cathode CL, $\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{ccl}}^{\text{aq}}$, as a function of p_{op} in the range 0–20 bar ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$). (d) Variation of pH_{acl} and $\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{ccl}}^{\text{aq}}$ as a function of p_{op} in the reduced range 0–2 bar ($I \approx 0.15 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$).

fundamentally different and compensating mechanisms. As demonstrated previously in Fig. 4, increasing temperature accelerates charge-transfer kinetics and improves ionic conductivity in the AEM and CLs, yielding lower kinetic and ohmic losses [83]. At the same time, however, temperature decreases CO_2 concentration sharply due to the decline of Henry's constant, a behavior also reported in experimental MEA studies by Ren et al. [25] and Giron-Rodríguez et al. [26]. Elevating cathode pressure counteracts this effect by boosting CO_2 solubility, in agreement with the pressure-dependent CO_2 RR observations of Huang et al. [29] and Girichandran et al. [28]. These opposing influences produce a diagonal ridge of enhanced performance, where pressure compensates for thermal solubility losses. The magenta star marks the location of the maximum ethylene-production current density, precisely where this balance is most favorable. This confirms that optimal operation does not emerge from independently maximizing temperature or pressure, but from achieving a coupled thermal-barometric balance. The influence of anolyte concentration becomes particularly evident in the CO_2 utilization contours of Fig. 9(c)–(d). Increasing the KOH concentration from 1 M to 5 M expands the high-current-density region because the larger OH^- reservoir improves ionic conduction and helps sustain alkaline operation under

demanding conditions. However, the stronger alkaline environment also intensifies carbonation reactions, causing a larger fraction of the dissolved CO_2 to react chemically into (bi)carbonate species rather than being converted electrochemically [15,31,41–43]. Therefore, although increasing KOH concentration improves electrochemical performance by lowering anodic and ionic losses, it simultaneously reduces carbon efficiency due to enhanced parasitic carbonation, in agreement with previous experimental and modeling studies [15,31–33].

Fig. 10(a)–(b) presents the contours of ethylene Faradaic efficiency across the temperature–pressure space. A clear optimum in $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ appears at intermediate pressures and low temperatures. This behavior is consistent with the trends seen earlier in Figs. 4 and 7. At low to moderate pressure, the increase in dissolved CO_2 enhances CO_2 RR and promotes CO surface coverage, strengthening the C–C coupling pathway. This pressure-driven gain in $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ is in agreement with earlier experimental observations by Huang et al. [29] and Girichandran et al. [28]. At the same time, low temperature favors higher $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ because HER selectivity increases with temperature, an effect clearly shown in Fig. 4(a) and reported by Ren et al. [25]. As temperature rises, HER becomes increasingly competitive, gradually suppressing ethylene selectivity even though reaction kinetics and ionic transport

Fig. 9. Interplay of operating temperature, T_{op} , and pressure, p_{op} , on several performance parameters at $V_{\text{cell}} = 3.5$ V. (a)–(b) Contours of the current density, I , for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively. (c)–(d) Contours of the CO₂ utilization, $U_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively.

accelerate. This explains why the $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ contours are skewed toward lower temperatures. A further decrease in ethylene FE at high pressure arises from the catalytic pathway shift toward formate, first identified in Fig. 7(a). Under excessive CO₂ supersaturation, the local CO₂ activity at the Cu surface becomes so large that the CO-mediated C – C coupling sequence is kinetically suppressed, enabling the CO₂-to-formate route. This mechanism, captured in the model via the multiproduct rate expression, matches experimental observations under high CO₂ chemical

potentials [29]. Moreover, the carbonation-induced OH[−] depletion and the increase in anode overpotential shown in Fig. 8 further degrade the microenvironment necessary for stable C₂H₄ formation, amplifying the loss in $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ at high pressure. Fig. 10(c)–(d) combines the contributions of current density, selectivity, and CO₂ utilization, revealing where ethylene production $I_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$ is maximized. Unlike $\text{FE}_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$, the ethylene production rate increases dramatically with temperature because current density grows strongly with T_{op} (due to faster kinetics

Fig. 10. Interplay of operating temperature, T_{op} , and pressure, p_{op} , on several performance parameters at $V_{cell} = 3.5$ V. (a)–(b) Contours of the ethylene Faradaic efficiency, $FE_{C_2H_4}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively. (c)–(d) Contours of the ethylene production rate, $I_{C_2H_4}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively.

and lower ohmic losses), as previously seen in Figs. 4(b) and 9(a)–(b). Similarly, pressure increases I through improved CO_2 solubility and mass transport. As a result, the optimal region for ethylene production shifts to high temperature and intermediate pressure, exactly where the enhancing influence of higher current density compensates for the decreasing $FE_{C_2H_4}$. This explains why the large magenta star in Fig. 10(d) lies at a much higher temperature than the $FE_{C_2H_4}$ maximum.

The influence of anolyte concentration is further clarified in Fig. 10 by comparing the operating maps obtained for 1 M and 5 M KOH. Increasing the KOH concentration expands the region of high ethylene production, particularly at elevated temperature and pressure, because the larger OH^- reservoir improves ionic conduction and reduces the transport limitations associated with hydroxide migration through the AEM and CLs [41,43,46]. This effect is especially

evident in Fig. 10(c)–(d), where the 5 M KOH case sustains larger $I_{C_2H_4}$ values over a broader operating domain. However, the stronger alkaline environment also intensifies carbonation reactions, particularly at high pressure where dissolved CO_2 concentrations are larger [15,31–33]. Consequently, although higher KOH concentration enhances ethylene productivity, it also increases carbonate formation and reduces carbon efficiency, highlighting once again the trade-off between electrochemical performance and carbonation in alkaline CO_2 electrolysis.

4.6.2. Coupled effect of operating RH and drag coefficient

Figs. 11 and 12 investigate the coupled influence of the cathode inlet relative humidity, RH_{op} , and the effective drag coefficient, f_{eod}^{eff} , on the performance at $V_{cell} = 3.5$ V. Together, these contour maps extend the multidimensional parametric analysis in Figs. 9 and 10 (temperature–pressure space) by probing the internal redistribution of water within the MEA, a key factor that regulates CO_2 transport, ionic conduction, and carbonation chemistry [88]. As demonstrated earlier in Fig. 5, water management plays an essential role in determining the balance between CO_2 availability, HER suppression, and mass-transport limitations in zero-gap CO_2 electrolyzers. Figs. 11 and 12 build on these earlier findings to provide a deeper, coupled view of how humidification and electro-osmotic drag jointly shape the cathode microenvironment, defining the practical operating window for stable and efficient C_2H_4 production. As before, the magenta star marks the operating point of maximum ethylene production (i.e., maximum C_2H_4 partial current density). The sign and magnitude of the electro-osmotic drag coefficient play a decisive role. A positive f_{eod}^{eff} enhances water transport from the anode to the cathode, hydrating the cathode CL (the typical scenario), whereas a negative f_{eod}^{eff} drives water from the cathode to the anode, favoring the dehydration of the cathode electrolyte. This two-way water flux becomes strongly coupled with the imposed RH_{op} , such that the hydration state of the cathode CL results from the combination of externally supplied vapor-phase water and internally transported membrane water.

Fig. 11(a)–(b) clearly shows that current density increases with cathode humidity and moderately positive drag values, reaching a sharp maximum at $RH_{op} \approx 0.9$ –1 and $f_{eod}^{eff} \approx 0$ –2, as indicated by the magenta star. At negative drag coefficients, the cathode loses water to the anode, leading to cathode dehydration, a reduction in ionomer water content, and impaired CO_2 dissolution, which together limit CO_2 availability and force a larger portion of the current toward HER. This behavior directly mirrors the dry-feed behavior reported in Fig. 5(a)–(b), where inadequate hydration caused suppressed CO_2RR activity and enhanced HER [71]. At the opposite extreme, very high positive drag values produce over-hydration and flooding, increasing liquid saturation in the CL and MPL/GDL and blocking gas-phase CO_2 transport, again decreasing the achievable current density [89,90]. The CO_2 utilization contours shown in Fig. 11(c)–(d) also exhibit a pronounced sensitivity to the hydration state set by RH_{op} and f_{eod}^{eff} , with losses at both extremes. When dehydration occurs at low RH_{op} and negative f_{eod}^{eff} , the ionomer water content drops, and the effective ionic conductivity decreases sharply, which limits the local electro-reduction rate. Under these ionically starved conditions, the dissolved CO_2 that does enter the CL is preferentially carbonated rather than reduced, so that a larger fraction of CO_2 is lost to (bi)carbonate formation, and utilization declines [72]. This behavior is fully consistent with the dry-cathode trends and the dehydration-induced performance penalties discussed for Fig. 5. Conversely, when flooding sets in at high RH_{op} and positive drag, the excess liquid saturation blocks gas-phase pathways and hinders CO_2 access to active sites, while the high local water activity promotes carbonation, again diverting dissolved CO_2 away from electro-reduction and reducing utilization [35]. This mirrors the flooding-driven mass-transport loss previously identified as a key failure mode for Cu-MEA cathodes [5,91]. Therefore, CO_2 utilization remains high only when drag is moderate, ensuring that ionic

conduction, CO_2 access, and carbonate chemistry are simultaneously balanced and that neither dehydration nor flooding is present.

Fig. 12(a)–(b) reveals that $FE_{C_2H_4}$ is maximized under the same hydration conditions that maximize CO_2 availability and minimize HER. Dehydration suppresses $FE_{C_2H_4}$ by lowering CO coverage and enabling HER-dominant operation, consistent with Fig. 4(a). Conversely, high drag flooding blocks gas-phase CO_2 transport, again lowering $FE_{C_2H_4}$, in agreement with the mass-transport-loss mechanisms observed experimentally in flooded Cu-MEA cathodes [15,33]. Importantly, for both RH and drag, $FE_{C_2H_4}$ is somewhat higher at 5 M KOH in the optimal hydration regime, reflecting the improved buffering of OH^- and the mitigation of pH gradients enabled by the higher alkalinity, effects consistent with the enhanced C_2 selectivity reported at high electrolyte concentrations [75]. However, in agreement with the carbonation findings discussed in Figs. 7–10, the higher anolyte concentration must be used cautiously because it also increases the propensity for carbonation and salt precipitation, a longstanding durability challenge in alkaline MEAs [32,33]. Fig. 12(c)–(d) identifies a single global optimum in ethylene production, again corresponding to the magenta star at $RH_{op} \approx 0.9$ –1 and $f_{eod}^{eff} \approx 0$ –2. At this point, the cathode is well hydrated but not flooded, CO_2 transport is unimpaired, OH^- availability remains adequate to sustain both OER and CO_2RR , and HER competition is minimized. The structure of this optimal region closely resembles the temperature–pressure optimal window in Figs. 9 and 10, underscoring a recurring theme in this study: maximal ethylene production emerges only when hydration, ionic conduction, CO_2 solubility, and carbonate chemistry are simultaneously balanced.

5. Conclusions

This work has presented a one-dimensional, two-phase, non-isothermal membrane electrode assembly (MEA) model that couples multiproduct Cu-cathode CO_2 reduction kinetics with membrane/ionomer transport, two-phase water management, heat effects, and full carbonate chemistry. The model reproduces polarization behavior, voltage-loss partitioning, and product distributions reported in the literature, and enables the construction of operability maps that rationalize performance, selectivity, and carbon efficiency in zero-gap electrolyzers.

From these maps, clear operating rules have been identified that reconcile competing trends. In the temperature–pressure space, current density increases with both variables, but ethylene selectivity is maximized at low temperature and intermediate pressure, as higher temperature enhances hydrogen evolution while excessive pressure promotes formate formation and accelerates carbonation and OH^- consumption. As a result, net ethylene production is maximized at high temperature and moderate pressure, where kinetic and ohmic benefits outweigh selectivity losses. In the humidification–drag space, performance is governed by a narrow hydration window. Cathode dehydration reduces ionic conductivity and increases hydrogen evolution, whereas over-hydration leads to flooding, restricts CO_2 transport, and enhances carbonation. High CO_2 utilization and ethylene selectivity are therefore achieved only when both dehydration and flooding are avoided. Finally, pH and anolyte concentration impose a delicate trade-off between electrochemical performance and carbon efficiency. Increasing KOH concentration improves ionic conductivity and facilitates hydroxide transport through the membrane and catalyst layers, thereby reducing ohmic losses and expanding the operating window for high current density and ethylene production. However, the stronger alkaline environment also accelerates carbonation reactions by promoting the conversion of dissolved CO_2 into (bi)carbonate species. As a result, highly concentrated electrolytes, such as 5 M KOH, become increasingly susceptible to carbonate accumulation and salt precipitation within the porous cathode structure.

By integrating electrochemistry, two-phase transport, and carbonate equilibria, this work has translated qualitative understanding into

Fig. 11. Interplay of operating relative humidity, RH_{op} , and effective drag factor, $f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}}$ on several performance parameters at $V_{\text{cell}} = 3.5$ V. (a)–(b) Contours of the current density, I , for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively. (c)–(d) Contours of the CO_2 utilization, $U_{\text{CO}_2^{\text{aq}}}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively.

quantitative operating windows and design rules for Cu-based MEA systems. These results are directly relevant for scale-up, as the model provides predictive insight into the sensitivity of performance to temperature, pressure, humidity, and ionic transport, enabling the design of flow-field architectures, humidification strategies, and membrane/drag configurations that maintain uniform operating conditions and avoid

local degradation in large-area devices. Thus, the framework supports the definition of stack-level set-points and control strategies required to maximize C_2 productivity while minimizing flooding and carbonation losses.

Overall, the study demonstrates that optimal performance emerges only from the simultaneous balance of hydration, gas transport, and

Fig. 12. Interplay of operating relative humidity, RH_{op} , and effective drag factor, $f_{\text{eff}}^{\text{eff}}$ on several performance parameters at $V_{\text{cell}} = 3.5$ V. (a)–(b) Contours of the ethylene Faradaic efficiency, $FE_{C_2H_4}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively. (c)–(d) Contours of the ethylene production rate, $I_{C_2H_4}$, for 1 M and 5 M KOH, respectively.

carbonate chemistry, explaining why practical operating windows are inherently narrow. Future extensions of the work should include the study of precipitation kinetics, solid-phase transport and 2D/3D spatial resolution, as the basis for predictive durability maps and closed-loop RH/drag/pressure control.

Nomenclature

Symbols

a	electrochemical specific surface area / m^{-1}
a_{lg}	liquid/gas specific surface area / m^{-1}

C	molar concentration / mol m^{-3}
$D_{i,j}$	molecular diffusivity of species i in species j / $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
E	activation energy / J mol^{-1}
E_i	specific energy of phase i / J kg^{-1}
F	Faraday constant ($96485.333 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$)
FE	Faradaic efficiency / –
$f_{\text{eod}}^{\text{eff}}$	effective drag coefficient / –
f_i	proportionality factor of $p_c - s$ curve (or diffusivity decreasing factor) / –
f_v	water volume fraction in ionomer / –
H	Henry's constant / mol m^{-3}
ΔH	enthalpy variation / J mol^{-1}
h_{lg}	specific latent heat of evaporation/condensation / J mol^{-1}
I	current density / A m^{-2}
IEC	ion-exchange capacity / mol kg^{-1}
i	current density / A m^{-2}
i_0	exchange current density / A m^{-2}
j_i	flux / SI units
K	permeability / m^2
K_i	equilibrium constant of homogeneous reaction i / SI units
K_{Laem}	membrane hydraulic permeability / m^2
k^{eff}	effective thermal conductivity / $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
$k_{e/c}$	evaporation/condensation mass transfer coefficient / m s^{-1}
k_i	rate constant of homogeneous reaction i / SI units
k_{ri}	relative permeability of phase i / –
$k_{\text{s,d}}$	sorption/desorption mass transfer coefficient / m s^{-1}
M_i	molecular mass of species i / kg mol^{-1}
m	van Genuchten's parameter / –
n	van Genuchten's parameter (or kinetics exponent) / –
n_d^{w}	electro-osmotic drag coefficient of water / –
p	static pressure / Pa
p_c	capillary pressure / Pa
p_{cb}	van Genuchten's parameter / Pa
R	universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
RH	relative humidity / –
r_p	pore radius / m
S_i	source term / SI units
s	liquid saturation / –
T	temperature / K
U	utilization / –
U_0	standard potential / V
u_i	superficial velocity of phase i / m s^{-1}
V_{cell}	cell voltage / V
V_i	molar volume of species i / $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
x	through-plane coordinate / m
x_i	mole fraction of species i / –
Y_i	mass fraction of species i / –
z_i	charge (valence) of ion i / –

Greek letters

α	charge-transfer coefficient / –
$\gamma_{e/c}$	evaporation/condensation rate coefficient / s^{-1}
δ	thickness / m
ε	porosity (or volume fraction) / –
η	overpotential / V
λ	electrolyte water content / –
μ	dynamic viscosity / $\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
ν	diffusion volume / –
Π	Peltier coefficient / V
ρ	density / kg m^{-3}
σ	(ionic or electronic) conductivity / S m^{-1}
τ	tortuosity / –
ϕ_e	electronic potential / V
ϕ_ℓ	ionic/electrolyte potential / V

Subscripts and superscripts

a	anode
ac	acidic
aem	anion-exchange membrane
alk	alkaline
aq	aqueous
atm	atmospheric
bpp	bipolar plate
bulk	bulk condition
c	cathode, condensation or capillary
cl	catalyst layer
ct	charge transfer
d	dissolved or desorption
dry	dry condition
e	electronic or evaporation
eff	effective
eod	electro-osmotic drag
eq	equilibrium
g	gas phase
gdl	gas diffusion layer
h	homogeneous
HER	hydrogen evolution reaction
k	kinetics
kn	knudsen
l	liquid phase
ℓ	electrolyte or ionic phase
m	membrane or electrolyte, maximum
mpl	microporous layer
OER	oxygen evolution reaction
p	pore
ptl	porous transport layer
r	residual, relative
red	reduced
ref	reference
rh	relative humidity
s	sorption
sat	saturated condition
tp	two-phase condition
w	water
wet	wet condition
0	standard/reference condition

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Pablo A. García-Salaberrí: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Cintia Casado:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Javier Marugán:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.149174>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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